

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
College of Engineering and Technology

SCHEME OF TEACHING AND EXAMINATION 2017-18

B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING

III SEMESTER

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	17SMA31	Engineering Mathematics-III	3	1		50	50	100	03
2	17SCV32	Building Materials and Construction Technology	3			50	50	100	03
3	17SCV33	Strength of Materials	4	1		50	50	100	04
4	17SCV34	Surveying-I	3			50	50	100	03
5	17SCV35	Fluid Mechanics	4	1		50	50	100	04
6	17SCV36	Applied Engineering Geology	3			50	50	100	03
7	17SCVL37	Material Testing Lab	1		2	50	50	100	02
8	17SCVL38	Surveying Practice-I	1		2	50	50	100	02
		Total Credits	22	03	04			800	24

B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING**IV SEMESTER**

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	17SMA41	Engineering Mathematics-IV	4	1		50	50	100	03
2	17SCV42	Structural Analysis I	4	1		50	50	100	04
3	17SCV43	Hydraulics & Hydraulic Machines	3	2		50	50	100	04
4	17SCV44	Concrete Technology	3			50	50	100	03
5	17SCV45	Surveying II	3			50	50	100	03
6	17SCV46	Building Planning & Drawing	3			50	50	100	03
7	17SCVL47	Surveying Practice II	1		2	50	50	100	02
8	17SCVL48	Applied Engineering Geology Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
		Total Credits	22	04	04			800	24

B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING**V SEMESTER**

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	17SCV51	Principles of Management & Entrepreneurship	3	1		50	50	100	03
2	17SCV52	Design of RCC Structural Elements	4	1		50	50	100	04
3	17SCV53	Structural Analysis – II	3	1		50	50	100	03
4	17SCV54	Geotechnical Engineering – I	3			50	50	100	03
5	17SCV55	Hydrology and Irrigation Engineering	3			50	50	100	03
6	17SCV56	Transportation Engineering – I	3			50	50	100	03
7	17SCVL57	Hydraulics and Hydraulic Machines Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
8	17SCVL58	Computer Aided Design Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
		Total Credits	22	03	04			800	23

B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING

VI SEMESTER

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	17SCV61	Environmental Engineering - I	4	1		50	50	100	04
2	17SCV62	Design & Drawing of RC Structures	3	1		50	50	100	03
3	17SCV63	Transportation Engineering – II	3			50	50	100	03
4	17SCV64X	Professional Elective-A	3			50	50	100	03
5	17SCV65X	Professional Elective-B	3			50	50	100	03
6	17SCV66X	Open Elective-I	3			50	50	100	03
7	17SCVL67	Geotechnical Engineering Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
8	17SCVL68	Civil Engineering Extensive Survey Project Work & Viva Voce	1		2	50	50	100	02
9	17SCVP69	Mini Project				50		50	02
Total Credits			22	02	04			850	25

Professional Elective-A		Open Elective-I	
17SCV641	Geotechnical Engineering – II	17SCV661	Occupational Health & Safety in Construction Industry
17SCV642	Urban Transport Planning	17SCV662	Air Pollution & Control
17SCV643	Structural Dynamics	17SCV663	Total Quality Management
Professional Elective-B			
17SCV651	Ground Improvement Techniques		
17SCV652	Principles of Construction Management		
17SCV653	Hydraulic Structures and Irrigation Design-Drawing		

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VII SEMESTER

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	17SCV71	Design of Steel Structures	4	1		50	50	100	04
2	17SCV72	Quantity Surveying and Valuation	3	1		50	50	100	03
3	17SCV73X	Professional Elective - C	3			50	50	100	03
4	17SCV74X	Professional Elective - D	3			50	50	100	03
5	17SCV75X	Open Elective - II	3			50	50	100	03
6	17SCVL76	Environmental Engineering Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
7	17SCVL77	Concrete & Highway Material Testing Laboratory	1		2	50	50	100	02
8	17SCVL78	Project Phase - I	1		3	100	-	100	02
Total Credits			19	2	7	450	350	800	22

Professional Elective-C		Open Elective-II	
17SCV731	Environmental Engineering - II	17SCV751	Water Resources Management
17SCV732	Design of Pre-Stressed Concrete Structures	17SCV752	Research Methodology
17SCV733	Masonry Structures	17SCV753	Principles of Town Planning
Professional Elective-D			
17SCV741	Environmental Impact Assessment		
17SCV742	Finite Element Method of Analysis		
17SCV743	Human Resources Management and development in Construction		

B.TECH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING**VIII SEMESTER**

Sl. No.	Subject code	Title	Teaching			Exam			Credits
			Theory	Tutorial	Lab	IA	Exam	TOTAL	
1	17SCV81	Design & Drawing of Steel Structure	4	2		50	50	100	04
2	17SCV82X	Professional Elective - E	3			50	50	100	03
3	17SCV83X	Open Elective - III	3			50	50	100	03
4	17SCV84	Technical Seminar		3		100		100	01
5	17SCV85	Major Project Phase - 2			6	100	100	300	08
6	17SCV86	Internship		2		50	50	100	02
		Total Credits	10	7	6	400	300	800	21

Professional Elective-E		Open Elective-III	
17SCV821	Pavement Design	17SCV831	Quality Assurance in Construction Projects
17SCV822	Highway Geometric Design	17SCV832	Building Services
17SCV823	Advanced Concrete Technology	17SCV833	Sustainability and Green Construction

III Semester B.Tech**BUILDING MATERIALS AND CONSTRUCTION TECHNOLOGY**

Sub Code : 17SCV32
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 4

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES

1. To develop in recognizing the good materials to be used for the construction work
2. To develop investigation of soil condition, deciding and design of suitable foundation for different structures
3. To develop supervision of different types of masonry
4. To impart in selection of materials, design and supervision of suitable type of floor and roof.
5. To gain knowledge about doors, windows, plastering, painting, damp proofing, scaffolding, shoring, underpinning and to take suitable engineering measures.

COURSE OUTCOMES

CO1: To understand the properties of natural and advance building materials

CO2: To impart the knowledge about the characteristics, sources and defects in various materials used for construction purposes.

CO3: Able to design and test the materials either in the laboratory or in the field before their actual use at the site.

CO4: To attain the knowledge of different components of building, their classification, materials and methods of construction and causes of their failures.

CO5: To understand the types and functions of main building services to be provided and the defects in the buildings along with the remedial measures for proper maintenance of the buildings.

MODULE-1**Introduction to Building Materials**

Stone as building material; Requirement of good building stones, dressing of stones, Deterioration and Preservation of stone work. Bricks; Classification, Manufacturing of clay bricks, Requirement of good bricks. Field and laboratory tests on bricks; compressive strength, water absorption, efflorescence, dimension and warpage. Cement Concrete blocks, Stabilized Mud Blocks, Sizes, requirement of good blocks. Mortar: types and requirements. Timber as construction material Fine aggregate: Natural and manufactured: Sieve analysis, zoning, specify gravity, bulking, moisture content, deleterious materials. Coarse aggregate: Natural and manufactured: Importance of size, shape and texture. Grading of aggregates, Sieve analysis, specific gravity, Flakiness and elongation index, crushing, impact and abrasion tests.

10 Hours**MODULE-2****Foundation**

Preliminary investigation of soil, safe bearing capacity of soil, Function and requirements of good foundation, types of foundation, introduction to spread, combined, strap, mat and pile foundation Masonry: Definition and terms used in masonry. Brick masonry, characteristics and requirements of good brick masonry, Bonds in brick work, Header, Stretcher, English, Flemish bond, Stone masonry, Requirements of good stonemasonry, Classification, characteristics of different stone masonry, Joints in stone masonry. Types of walls; load bearing, partition walls, cavity walls

10 Hours

MODULE-3

Lintels and Arches

Lintels and Arches: Definition, function and classification of lintels, Balconies, chejja and canopy. Arches; Elements and Stability of an Arch.

Floors and roofs: Floors; Requirement of good floor, Components of ground floor, Selection of flooring material, Laying of Concrete, Mosaic, Marble, Granite, Tile flooring, Cladding of tiles. Roof;- Requirement of good roof, Types of roof, Elements of a pitched roof, Trussed roof, Kingpost Truss, Queen Post Truss, Steel Truss, Different roofing materials, R.C.C Roof. **10 hours**

MODULE-4

Doors, Windows and Ventilators

Doors, Windows and Ventilators: Location of doors and windows, technical terms, Materials for doors and windows, Paneled door, Flush door, Collapsible door, Rolling shutter, PVC Door, Paneled and glazed Window, Bay Window, French window. Ventilators. Sizes as per IS recommendations.

Stairs: Definitions, technical terms and types of stairs, Requirements of good stairs. Geometrical design of RCC doglegged and open-well stairs.

Formwork: Introduction to form work, scaffolding, shoring, under pinning. **10 hours**

MODULE-5

Plastering and Pointing

Plastering and Pointing: Purpose, materials and methods of plastering and pointing, defects in plastering- Stucco plastering, lathe plastering.

Damp proofing-causes, effects and methods.

Paints-Purpose, types, ingredients and defects, Preparation and applications of paints to new and old plastered surfaces, wooden and steel surfaces. **10 hours**

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

TEXT BOOKS

1. **Engineering Materials**, Rangawala P.C. Charter Publishing House, Anand, India.
2. **Engineering Materials**, Sushil Kumar, Standard Publication and Distributors, New Delhi.
3. **Concrete Technology – Theory and practice**, M.S. Shetty, S. Chand and Co, New Delhi, 2002.

REFERENCE BOOKS

1. **A Text Book Building Materials**, by P.G. Varghese, Prentice-Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., Publication.
2. **Advances in Building Materials and Construction** by Mohan Rai and M.P. Jain Singh – publication by CBRI, Roorkee.
3. **Concrete Technology**, Neville A.M and Brooks J.J — ELBS Edition. London
4. **Concrete Technology – Gambhir M.L –Dhanpat Rai and Sons, New Delhi.**

III Semester B.Tech
STRENGTH OF MATERIALS

Sub Code : 17SCV33
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 4

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To learn fundamental concepts of stress, strain and deformation of solids with applications to bars, beams and thin shells.
2. To know the mechanism of load transfer in beams, the induced stress resultants and deformations.
3. To understand the effect of torsion on shafts and springs.
4. To analyze two dimensional state of stress and plane trusses.
5. To give an ability to apply the knowledge of strength of materials on engineering applications and design problems.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to apply the linear laws of elasticity as related to stresses and strains.

CO2: Able to understand the behavior of columns and struts under axial loading and also the effect of combined axial and bending stress.

CO3: Able to provide students with exposure to the systematic methods for solving engineering problems in solid mechanics.

CO4: Able to analyze and design structural members subjected to tension, compression, torsion, bending and combined stresses using the fundamental concepts of stress, strain and elastic behavior of materials.

CO5: Able to build the necessary theoretical background for further structural analysis

MODULE 1:**Simple Stress and Strain**

Introduction, Definition and concept and of stress and strain. Hooke's law, Stress-Strain diagrams for ferrous and non-ferrous materials, factor of safety, Elongation of tapering bars of circular and rectangular cross sections, Elongation due to self-weight. Saint Venant's principle, Compound bars, Temperature stresses, Compound section subjected to temperature stresses, state of simple shear, Elastic constants and their relationship.

10 Hours**MODULE 2:****Compound Stresses**

Introduction, state of stress at a point, General two dimensional stress system, Principal stresses and principal planes. Mohr's circle of stresses.

Thin and Thick Cylinders:

Introduction, Thin cylinders subjected to internal pressure; Hoop stresses, Longitudinal stress and change in volume. Thick cylinders subjected to both internal and external pressure; Lamé's equation, radial and hoop stress distribution.

10 Hours

MODULE 3:

Shear Force and Bending Moment in Beams

Introduction to types of beams, supports and loadings. Definition of bending moment and shear force, Sign conventions, relationship between load intensity, bending moment and shear force. Shear force and bending moment diagrams for statically determinate beams subjected to points load, uniformly distributed loads, uniformly varying loads, couple and their combinations. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4:

Bending and Shear Stresses in Beams

Introduction, pure bending theory, Assumptions, derivation of bending equation, modulus of rupture, section modulus, flexural rigidity. Expression for transverse shear stress in beams, Bending and shear stress distribution diagrams for circular, rectangular, 'I', and 'T' sections. Shear center (only concept)

Columns and Struts:

Introduction, short and long columns. Euler's theory; Assumptions, Derivation for Euler's Buckling load for different end conditions, Limitations of Euler's theory. Rankine -Gordon's formula for columns.

10 Hours

MODULE 5:

Torsion in Circular Shaft

Torsion in Circular Shaft: Introduction, pure torsion, Assumptions, derivation of torsion equation for circular shafts, torsional rigidity and polar modulus Power transmitted by a shaft, combined bending and torsion.

Theories of Failure: Introduction, maximum principal stress theory (Rankine's theory), Maximum shearing stress theory (Tresca's theory), Strain energy theory (Beltrami and Haigh), and maximum strain theory (St. Venant's theory). **10 Hours**

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Strength of Materials**, Subramanyam, Oxford University Press, Edition 2008
2. **Mechanics of Materials**, B.C Punmia Ashok Jain, Arun Jain, Lakshmi Publications, New Delhi.
3. **Strength of Materials**, Basavarajaiah and Mahadevappa Universities Press (2009).

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Strength of Materials**, Singer Harper and Row Publications.
2. **Elements of Strength of Materials**, Timoshenko and Young Affiliated East-West Press.
3. **Mechanics of Materials**, James M. Gere (5th Edition), Thomson Learning.

III Semester B.Tech**SURVEYING – I****Sub Code : 17SCV34****Hrs/ Week : 3****Credits : 3****IA Marks : 50****Exam Hours : 2****Exam Marks: 50****Total Hours : 50****COURSE OBJECTIVES:**

1. To determine the relative position of any objects or points of the earth.
2. To determine the distance and angle between different objects.
3. To prepare a map or plan to represent an area on a horizontal plan.
4. To develop methods through the knowledge of modern science and the technology and use them in the field.
5. To solve measurement problems in an optimal way.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to understand the different methods and techniques of surveying like levelling, compass survey, contouring and curve settings etc. and their applications in surveying.

CO2: Able to use survey instruments in carrying out survey, to collect data, and write reports and able to perform required calculations to achieve the objective for different types of surveying for different Engineering projects.

CO3: Able to apply the concept of Tacheometry for surveying in difficult and hilly areas to obtain the topographical map of area.

CO4: Able to control the accumulation of errors in projects.

CO5: Able to use modern survey equipment to measure angle and distances.

MODULE 1:**Introduction to Civil Engineering Surveying**

Introduction: Definition of surveying, Objectives and importance of surveying. Classification of surveys. Principles of surveying. Units of measurements, Surveying measurements and errors, types of errors, precision and accuracy. Classification of maps, map scale, conventional symbols, topographic maps, map layout, Survey of India Map numbering systems.

Measurement of Horizontal Distances: Measuring tape and types. Measurement using tapes, taping on level ground and sloping ground. Errors and corrections in tape measurements, ranging of lines, direct and indirect methods of ranging, Electronic distance measurement, basic principle. Booking of tape survey work, Field book, entries, Conventional symbols, Obstacles in tape survey, Numerical problems.

10 Hours**MODULE 2:****Measurement of Directions and Angles**

Compass survey: Basic definitions; meridians, bearings, magnetic and true bearings. Prismatic and surveyor's compasses, temporary adjustments, declination. Quadrantal bearings, whole circle bearings, local attraction and related problems

Theodolite Survey and Instrument Adjustment: Theodolite and types, Fundamental axes and parts of Transit theodolite, uses of theodolite, Temporary adjustments of transit theodolite, measurement of horizontal and vertical angles, step by step procedure for obtaining permanent adjustment of Transit theodolite

10 Hours

MODULE 3:

Traversing

Traverse Survey and Computations: Latitudes and departures, rectangular coordinates, Traverse adjustments, Bowditch rule and transit rule, Numerical Problems

Tacheometry: basic principle, types of tachometry, distance equation for horizontal and inclined line of sight infixed hair method, problems **10 Hours**

MODULE 4:

Leveling

Basic terms and definitions, Methods of leveling, Dumpy level, auto level, digital and laser levels. Curvature and refraction corrections. Booking and reduction of levels. Differential leveling, profile leveling, fly leveling, check leveling, reciprocal leveling, trigonometric leveling (heights and distances-single plane and double plane methods.

Contouring: Contours, Methods of contouring, Interpolation of contours, contour gradient, characteristics of contours and uses. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5:

Areas and Volumes

Areas and Volumes: Measurement of area – by dividing the area into geometrical figures, area from offsets, mid ordinate rule, trapezoidal and Simpson's one third rule, area from co-ordinates, introduction to planimeter, principle of working and use of planimeter to measure areas, digital planimeter. Measurement of volumes-trapezoidal and prismoidal formula. Calculation of area from cross staff surveying, Calculation of area of a closed traverse by coordinates method; Computations of volumes by trapezoidal and prismoidal rule, Capacity contours. **10 Hours**

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

TEXT BOOKS:

1. 'Surveying' Vol-1 – B.C. Punmia, Laxmi Publications, New Delhi.
2. Surveying and Levelling – R Subramanian. Oxford University Press (2007)
- Text Book of Surveying – C. Venkataramiah. Universities Press. (2009Reprint)

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Fundamentals of Surveying - Milton O. Schimidt – Wong, Thomson Learning.
 2. Fundamentals of Surveying - S.K. Roy – Prentice Hall of India.
 3. Surveying Vol. I, S.K. Duggal, Tata McGraw Hill - Publishing Co. Ltd., New Delhi.
- * Survey of India Publication on maps.

**III Semester B.Tech
FLUID MECHANICS**

Sub Code : 17SCV35
Hrs/ Week : 3
Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To impart thorough understanding of the properties of the fluids, behavior of fluids under static conditions.
2. To develop understanding about hydrostatic law, principle of buoyancy and stability of a floating body and application of mass, momentum and energy equation in fluid flow
3. The dynamics of fluids is introduced through the control volume approach which gives an integrated understanding of the transport of mass, momentum and energy.
4. To expose to the applications of the conservation laws to a) flow measurements b) flow through pipes (both laminar and turbulent)
5. To determine the losses in a flow system, flow through pipes, boundary layer flow and flow past immersed bodies.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: To describe appropriate physical properties and show how these allow differentiation between solids and fluids as well as between liquids and gases.
- CO2: Able to determine pressures and forces on submerged bodies.
- CO3: Able to analyze flow rates, velocities, energy losses and momentum flux for fluid system and also understand the fundamentals of laminar and turbulent boundary layer.
- CO4: To present data or governing equations in non-dimensional form, design experiments, and perform model studies.
- CO5: Able to decide when appropriate to use ideal flow concepts and the Bernoulli equation.

MODULE 1:**Fluids & Their Properties**

Fluids & Their Properties: Concept of fluid, Systems of units. Properties of fluid; Mass density, Specific weight, Specific gravity, Specific volume, Viscosity, Cohesion, Adhesion, Surface tension & Capillarity. Fluid as a continuum, Newton's law of viscosity (theory & problems). Capillary rise in a vertical tube and between two plane surfaces (theory & problems). Vapor pressure of liquid, compressibility and bulk modulus, capillarity, surface tension, pressure inside a water droplet, pressure inside a soap bubble and liquid jet. Numerical problems.

Fluid Pressure and Its Measurements: Definition of pressure, Pressure at a point, Pascal's law, Variation of pressure with depth. Types of pressure. Measurement of pressure using simple, differential & inclined manometers (theory & problems). Introduction to Mechanical and electronic pressure measuring devices.

10 Hours**MODULE 2:****Hydrostatic forces on Surfaces**

Hydrostatic forces on Surfaces: Definition, Total pressure, center of pressure, total pressure on horizontal, vertical and inclined plane surface, total pressure on curved surfaces, water pressure on gravity dams, Lock gates. Numerical Problems.

Fundamentals of fluid flow (Kinematics): Introduction. Methods of describing fluid motion. Velocity and Total acceleration of a fluid particle. Types of fluid flow, Description of flow pattern. Basic principles of fluid flow, three-dimensional continuity equation in Cartesian coordinate system. Derivation for

Rotational and irrotational motion. Potential function, stream function, orthogonality of streamlines and equipotential lines. Numerical problems on Stream function and velocity potential. Introduction to flow net. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3:

Fluid Dynamics

Fluid Dynamics: Introduction. Forces acting on fluid in motion. Euler's equation of motion along a streamline and Bernoulli's equation. Assumptions and limitations of Bernoulli's equation. Modified Bernoulli's equation. Problems on applications of Bernoulli's equation (with and without losses). Vortex motion; forced vortex, free vortex, problems. Momentum equation problems on pipe bends.

Applications: Introduction. Venturimeter, Orificemeter, Pitot tube. Numerical Problems **10 Hours**

MODULE 4:

Orifice and Mouthpiece

Orifice and Mouthpiece: Introduction, classification, flow through orifice, hydraulic coefficients, and Numerical problems. Mouthpiece, classification, Borda's Mouthpiece.

Notches and Weirs: Introduction. Classification, discharge over rectangular, triangular, trapezoidal notches, Cippoletti notch, broad crested weirs. Numerical problems. Ventilation of weirs, submerged weirs. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5:

Flow through Pipes

Flow through Pipes: Introduction. Major and minor losses in pipe flow. Darcy-Weisbach equation for head loss due to friction in a pipe. Pipes in series, pipes in parallel, equivalent pipe-problems. Minor losses in pipe flow, equation for head loss due to sudden expansion. Numerical problems. Hydraulic gradient line, energy gradient line. Pipe Networks, Hardy Cross method, Numerical problems.

Surge Analysis in Pipes: Water hammer in pipes, equations for pressure rise due to gradual valve closure and sudden closure for rigid and elastic pipes. Numerical problems. **10 Hours**

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

TEXT BOOKS:

1. 'A Text Book of Fluid mechanics & Hydraulic Machines'- R.K. Rajput, S. Chand & Co, New Delhi, 2006 Edition.
2. 'Principles of Fluid Mechanics and Fluid Machines'-N. Narayana Pillai, Universities Press (India), Hyderabad, 2009 Edition.
3. 'Fluid Mechanics and Turbomachines'- Madan Mohan Das, PHI Learning Pvt. Limited, New Delhi. 2009 Edition.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. 'Fundamentals of Fluid Mechanics' – Bruce R. Munson, Donald F. Young, Theodore H. Okiishi, Wiley India, New Delhi, 2009 Edition.
2. 'Introduction To Fluid Mechanics' – Edward J. Shaughnessy, Jr; Ira M. Katz; James P. Schaffer, Oxford University Press, New Delhi, 2005 Edition.
3. 'Text Book of Fluid Mechanics & Hydraulic Machines'-R.K. Bansal, Laxmi Publications, New Delhi, 2008 Edition.
4. 'Fluid Mechanics' – Streeter, Wylie, Bedford New Delhi, 2008 (Ed)

III Semester B.Tech
APPLIED ENGINEERING GEOLOGY

Sub Code : 17SCV36
Hrs/ Week : 3
Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. At the end of this course the students will be able to understand the importance of geological knowledge such as earth, earthquake, volcanism and the action of various geological agencies.
2. The students of civil engineering will realize the importance of this knowledge in projects such as dams, tunnels, roads etc.
3. The knowledge of geophysical methods and remote sensing techniques are useful to know the various surface and subsurface features.
4. Based on this, civil engineers can choose the types of foundations and other related aspects.
5. The students of civil engineering will be able to identify the physical properties and strength of rocks.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to understand the importance of geological knowledge such as earthquake, volcanism

CO2: Able to learn geology and its types, various structural features like folds, faults, joints, weathering etc., minerals, rocks, and rock formations in relation to civil engineering projects.

CO3: Able to understand various techniques to determine engineering properties of rocks etc. and distinguish the different types of rocks and minerals.

CO4: Able to understand various techniques to analyze and to make possible solutions for various Geological Engineering problems.

CO5: Able to understand the application of geological investigation in projects such as dams, tunnels etc.

MODULE 1**Introduction:**

Application of Earth Science in Civil Engineering Practices, Understanding the earth, internal structure and composition.

Mineralogy: Mineral properties, composition and their use in the manufacture of construction materials – Quartz Group (Glass); Feldspar Group (Ceramic wares and Flooring tiles); Kaolin (Paper, paint and textile);Asbestos (AC sheets); Carbonate Group (Cement) ;Gypsum (POP, gypsum sheets, cement); Mica Group(Electrical industries); Ore minerals - Iron ores(Steel); Chromite (Alloy); Bauxite (aluminum);Chalcopyrite (copper) **10 Hours**

MODULE 2**Petrology**

Formation, Classification and Engineering Properties. Rock as construction material, concrete aggregate, railway ballast, roofing, flooring, cladding and foundation. Deformation of rocks, Development of Joints, Folds, Faults and Unconformities. Their impact in the selection of sites for Dams, Reservoirs, Tunnels, Highways and Bridges, Rock Quality Determination (RQD), Rock Structure Rating (RSR),:Igneous Rocks - Granite, Gabbro, Dolerite, Basalt; Sedimentary rocks - Sandstone, Shale, Limestone, Laterite; Metamorphic rocks - Gneiss, Quartzite, Slate, Charnockite: Decorative stones - Porphyries, Marble and Quartzite. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3**Geomorphology and Seismology**

Landforms – Classification, Rock weathering, types and its effects on Civil Engineering Projects. Study of Geo-morphological aspects in the selection of sites for Dams, Reservoirs, Tunnels, Highways and Bridges. Watershed management, Floods and their control, River valley, Drainage pattern – parameters and development; Coastlines and their engineering considerations. Earthquake - Causes and Effects,, Seismic waves, Engineering problems related to Earthquakes, Earthquake intensity, Richter Scale, Seismograph, Seismic zones- World and India, Tsunami – causes and effects. Early warning system. Reservoir Induced Seismicity; Landslides – causes and their control. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4**Hydrogeology**

Hydrological cycle, Occurrence of Groundwater indifferent terrains -Weathered, Hard and Stratified rocks; Determination of Quality aspects - SAR, RSC and TH of Groundwater. Groundwater Pollution, Groundwater Exploration- Electrical Resistivity and Seismic methods, Resistivity curves, Water Bearing Formations, Aquifer types and parameters -Porosity, Specific yield and retention, Permeability, Transmissibility and Storage Coefficient. Springs and Artesian Wells, Artificial Recharging of Groundwater, Sea water intrusion and remedies. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5**Geodesy**

Study of Topographic maps and Contour maps; Remote Sensing – Concept, Application and its Limitations; Geographic Information System (GIS)and Global Positioning System (GPS) – Concept and their use resource mapping. LANDSAT Imagery –Definition and its use. Impact of Mining, Quarrying and Reservoirs on Environment. Natural Disasters and their mitigation. **10 Hours**

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

References books:

1. Text book of Geology by P.K. Mukherjee, World Press Pvt. Ltd. Kolkatta.
1. Foundations of Engineering Geology, by Tony Waltham (3rdEd.) Universities Press.
2. Structural Geology (3rd Ed.)By M. P. Billings, Published by Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi
3. Text of Engineering and General Geology by Parbin Singh, Published by S. K. Kataria and Sons, New Delhi.
4. Rock Mechanics for Engineers by Dr B.P.Verma, Khanna Publishers, New Delhi.
5. Engineering Geology for Civil Engineering by D. Venkata Reddy, Oxford and IBH Publishing Company, New Delhi.
6. Ground water geology by Todd D.K. John Wiley and Sons, New York.
7. Remote sensing Geology by Ravi P Gupta, Springer Verilag, New York.
8. Physical Geology by Arthur Holmes, Thomson Nelson and Sons, London.
9. Environmental Geology by K. S. Valdiya, Tata Mc Graw Hills.
10. A text book of Engineering Geology by Chenna Kesavulu, Mac Millan India Ltd.
11. Remote sensing and GIS by M.Anji Reddy.
12. Ground water assessment, development and management byK.R.Karant, Tata Mc Graw Hills

**III Semester B.Tech
MATERIAL TESTING LAB**

Sub Code : 17SCVL37
Hrs/ Week : 2L+1T
Credits : 2

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 3
Exam Marks: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To understand the characteristics of materials used in construction.
2. To understand the behavior of civil engineering materials used in buildings under different loading conditions.
3. To understand the importance of grading of aggregates
4. To operate and practical exposure of UTM to conduct test on various building materials
5. To demonstrate strain gauges and strain indicators

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Able to study the stress-strain curves of different materials used in the field under different loading conditions.
- CO2: Able to differentiate between properties of materials affect strength under various conditions.
- CO3: Able to calculate simple tensile and shear stress using the appropriate guidelines and formats.
- CO4: Able to analyze the bending stress on different types of sections.
- CO5: Able to understand deflection of different sections at different loading conditions.

EXPERIMENTS

1. Tension test on Mild steel and HYSD bars.
2. Compression test of Mild Steel, Cast iron and Wood.
3. Torsion test on Mild Steel circular sections
4. Bending Test on Wood Under two point loading
5. Shear Test on Mild steel.
6. Impact test on Mild Steel (Charpy & Izod)
7. Hardness tests on ferrous and non-ferrous metals – Brinell's, Rockwell and Vicker's
8. Test on Bricks and Tiles
9. Tests on Fine aggregates – Moisture content, Specific gravity, Bulk density, Sieve analysis and Bulking
10. Tests on Coarse aggregates – Absorption, Moisture content, specific gravity, Bulk density and Sieve analysis
11. Demonstration of Strain gauges and Strain indicators

NOTE: All tests to be carried out as per relevant BIS Codes

Scheme of Examination:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks
ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks
Viva – voce = 10 marks
Total: 50 marks

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Testing of Engineering Materials**, Davis, Troxell and Hawk, International Student Edition – McGraw Hill Book Co. New Delhi.
2. **Mechanical Testing of Materials**”, Fenner, George Newnes Ltd. London.
3. **“Experimental Strength of Materials”**, Holes K A, English Universities Press Ltd. London.
4. **“Testing of Metallic Materials”**, Surya narayana A K, Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.
5. **Relevant IS Codes**
6. **“Material Testing Laboratory Manual”**, Kukreja C B- Kishore K. Ravi Chawla Standard Publishers & Distributors 1996.
7. **Concrete Manual**, M.L. Gambhir –Dhanpat Rai & Sons- New Delhi.

III Semester B.Tech
SURVEYING PRACTICE – I

Sub Code : 17SCVL38
Hrs/ Week : 2L+1T
Credits : 2

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 3
Exam Marks: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To determine the relative position of any objects or points of the earth.
2. To determine the distance and angle between different objects.
3. To prepare a map or plan to represent an area on a horizontal plan.
4. To develop methods through the knowledge of modern science and the technology and use them in the field.
5. To solve measurement problems in an optimal way.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to Prepare the survey sheet according to the method used.

CO2: Able to apply theoretical considerations in field and other engineering projects.

CO3: Able to survey the area using different methods of plane tabling and compass survey and to adjust the compass traverse graphically.

CO4: Able to record the reduced levels using various methods of levelling and measurement of horizontal; vertical angles by Theodolite.

CO5: Able to determine the location of any point horizontally and vertically using Tachometry

EXPERIMENTS

- 1: a) To measure distance between two points using direct ranging
b) To set out perpendiculars at various points on given line using cross staff, optical square and tape.
- 2: Setting out of rectangle, hexagon using tape/chain and other accessories
- 3: Measurement of bearing of the sides of a closed traverse & adjustment of closing error by Bowditch method and Transit method
- 4: To set out rectangles, pentagon, hexagon, using tape /chain and compass.
- 5: To determine the distance between two inaccessible points using chain/tape& compass.
- 6: To locate points using radiation and intersection method of plane tabling
- 7: To solve 3-point problem in plane tabling using Bessel's graphical solution
- 8: To determine difference in elevation between two points using fly leveling technique & to conduct fly back leveling. Booking of levels using both HI and Rise & Fall methods.
- 9: To determine difference in elevation between two points using reciprocal leveling and to determine the collimation error

10: To conduct profile leveling for water supply /sewage line and to draw the longitudinal section to determine the depth of cut and depth of filling for a given formation level.

Demonstration

Minor instruments – Clinometer, Ceylon ghat tracer, Hand level, Box sextant, Planimeter and Pantagraph.

Scheme of Examination:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. ‘**Surveying**’ Vol.–1, B.C. Punmia, Laxmi Publications, New Delhi.
2. ‘**Plane Surveying**’ Vol-1-A.M. Chandra, Newage International ®Ltd.
3. ‘**Plane Surveying**’ – ALAK, S. Chand and Company Ltd., NewDelhi.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Fundamentals of Surveying** - S.K. Roy – Prentice Hall of India.
2. **Fundamentals of Surveying** - Milton O. Schimidt – Wong, Thomson Learning.
4. **Surveying** Vol. I, S.K. Duggal

**IV Semester B.Tech
STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS –I**

Sub Code : 17SCV42	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 4	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 4	Exam Marks: 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To impart the principles of elastic structural analysis and behavior of determinate structures.
2. To impart knowledge about various methods involved in the analysis of determinate structures.
3. To apply these methods for analyzing the indeterminate structures to evaluate the response of structures
4. To enable the student get a feeling of how real-life structures behave
5. To make the student familiar with latest computational techniques and software used for structural analysis.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1 Able to interpret the various methods of structural displacements.
 CO2 Able to analyze the determinate structure and its reaction diagram.
 CO3 Able to draw the influence line diagram for rolling loads.
 CO4 Able to compute the pressure on supporting tower, suspension bridge etc. and to calculate loads for no tension criteria on domes chimneys and retaining walls.
 CO5 Able to interpret the various methods of structural displacements.

MODULE 1

STRUCTURAL SYSTEMS AND ENERGY CONCEPT

Forms of structures, Conditions of equilibrium, Degree of freedom, Linear and Nonlinear structures, one, two, three dimensional structural systems, Determinate and indeterminate structures [Static and Kinematics]. Strain energy and complimentary strain energy, Strain energy due to axial load, bending and shear, Theorem of minimum potential energy, Law of conservation of energy, Principle of virtual work, **DEFLECTION OF BEAMS** Moment area method, Conjugate beam method

12Hours

MODULE 2

DEFLECTION OF BEAMS AND FRAMES BY STRAIN ENERGY

The first and second theorem of Castigliano, problems on beams, frames and trusses, Betti's law, Clarke - Maxwell's theorem of reciprocal deflection.

ANALYSIS OF BEAMS AND PLANE TRUSSES BY STRAIN ENERGY Analysis of beams (Propped cantilever and fixed beams) and trusses using strain energy and unit load methods

12 Hours

MODULE 3

ARCHES AND CABLES

Three hinged circular and parabolic arches with supports at same level and different levels, Determination of thrust, shear and bending moment, Analysis of cables under point loads and UDL, length of cables (Supports at same levels and at different levels).

10 Hours

MODULE 4

ANALYSIS OF BEAMS

Consistent deformation method – Propped cantilever and fixed beams

06 Hours

MODULE 5

Clapeyron's theorem of three moments – continuous beams and fixed beams

ANALYSIS OF ARCHES

Two hinged parabolic arch, two hinged Circular Arch

10 Hours

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Theory of Structures**, Pandit and Guptha, Vol. – I, Tata McGraw Hill, New Delhi.
2. **Basic Structural Analysis** Reddy C. S., Tata McGraw Hill, New Delhi.
3. **Strength of Materials and theory of structures** Vol I & II, B.C. Purnia, R.K., Jain Laxmi Publication New Delhi

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Elementary Structural Analysis**, Norris and Wilbur, International Student Edition. McGraw Hill Book Co: New York
2. **Structural Analysis**, 4th SI Edition by Amit Prasanth & Aslam Kassimali, Thomson Learning.
3. **Analysis of Structures**, Thandava Murthy, Oxford University Press,

IV Semester B.Tech
HYDRAULICS & HYDRAULIC MACHINES

Sub Code : 17SCV43	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 3	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 4	Exam Marks : 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To make the student /learn about the model and prototype relationship and able to predict the prototype behavior by model testing in the laboratory.
2. To impart knowledge about the working and design aspects of hydraulic machines like turbines and pumps and their applications.
3. To make the student confident in the fundamental concepts of open channel hydraulics.
4. To impart the knowledge of impact of jet of water on vanes
5. Imparts the knowledge of heads and efficiencies of pumps and turbines

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Student will be able to develop empirical relationships amongst physical variables involved in any physical flow phenomenon.
- CO2: Student will be able to design various components of pumps and turbines and study their characteristics
- CO3: Student will be able to develop velocity triangles on different vanes.
- CO4 Able to classify the flow in open channel and various momentum principles in open channels.
- CO5 Able to compute water surface profile by different approaches and to analyze hydraulic jump and energy dissipation.

MODULE-1**DIMENSIONAL ANALYSIS AND MODEL STUDIES**

Introduction, Systems of units, Dimensions of quantities, Dimensional Homogeneity of an equation. Analysis- Rayleigh's method, Buckingham's II theorem- problems. Model Studies, Similitude, Non-dimensional numbers: Froude models-Undistorted and Distorted models. Reynolds's models-Problems

10 Hours**MODULE 2****UNIFORM FLOW IN OPEN CHANNELS**

Introduction, Geometric properties of Rectangular, Triangular, Trapezoidal and Circular channels. Chezy's equation, Manning's equation-problems. Most economical open channels-Rectangular, Triangular, Trapezoidal and Circular channels- problems.

10**Hours****MODULE 3****NON-UNIFORM FLOW IN OPEN CHANNELS**

Introduction, Specific energy, Specific energy diagram, Critical depth, Conditions for Critical flow- Theory & problems. Hydraulic jump in a Horizontal Rectangular Channel- Theory and problems. Dynamic equation for Non-Uniform flow in an Open channel.

10 Hours

MODULE 4**IMPACT OF JET ON FLAT VANES**

Introduction, Impulse- Momentum equation. Direct impact of a jet on a stationary flat plate, Oblique impact of a jet on a stationary flat plate, direct impact on a moving plate, direct impact of a jet on a series of a jet on a series of flat vanes on a wheel. Conditions for maximum hydraulic efficiency. Impact of a jet on a hinged flat plate- problems.

IMPACT OF JET ON CURVED VANES

Introduction, Force exerted by a jet on a fixed curved vane, moving curved vane. Introduction to concept of velocity triangles, Impact of jet on a series of curved vanes-problems.

10 Hours**MODULE 5****PELTON WHEEL**

Introduction to Turbines, Classification of Turbines. Pelton wheel- components, working and velocity triangles. Maximum power, efficiency, working proportions- problems.

KAPLAN TURBINES

Introduction, Components, Working and Velocity triangles, Properties of the Turbine, Discharge of the Turbines, Number of Blades-Problems. Draft Tube: Types, efficiency of a Draft tube. Introduction to Cavitation in Turbines.

CENTRIFUGAL PUMPS

Introduction, Classification, Priming, Heads and Efficiencies. Equation for work done, minimum starting speed, velocity triangles. Multistage Centrifugal Pumps (Pumps in Series and Pumps in parallel). Problems.

10 Hours**Scheme of Examination:**

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

TEXT BOOKS:

1. 'A Text Book of Fluid mechanics & Hydraulic Machines'- R.K. Rajput, S. Chand & Co, New Delhi, 2006 Edition.
2. 'Text Book of Fluid Mechanics & Hydraulic Machines'-R.K. Bansal, Laxmi Publications, New Delhi, 2008 Edition.
3. 'Fluid Mechanics and Turbo machines'- Madan Mohan Das, PHI Learning Pvt. Limited, New Delhi. 2009 Edition.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. 'Introduction to Fluid Mechanics' – Robert w. Fox: Philip j. Pritchard: Alan t. McDonald, Wiley India, New Delhi, 2009 Edition.
2. 'Introduction To Fluid Mechanics' – Edward j. Shaughnessy, jr; Ira m. Katz; James p Schaffer, Oxford University Press, New Delhi, 2005 Edition
3. 'Hydraulics and Fluid Mechanics' – Dr. P.N. Modi & Dr S.M. Seth, Standard Book House- New Delhi. 2009 Edition.

**IV Semester B.Tech
CONCRETE TECHNOLOGY**

Sub Code : 17SCV44
Hrs/ Week : 3
Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. Understand properties of concrete and types of concrete
2. Know the procedure to determine the properties of fresh and hardened of concrete
3. To understand factors affecting the strength, workability and durability of concrete
4. Gain ideas on non-destructive testing of concrete and to impart the methods of proportioning of concrete mixtures
5. Gives ideas on the construction and inspection requirements the buildings

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to describe about composition and characteristics of Portland cement.

CO2: Able to classify the aggregate and their various properties.

CO3: Able to identify the various properties of concrete and analyzing its workability.

CO4: Able to illustrate design philosophies.

CO5: Able to understand various factors affecting the durability of infrastructures

Module-1

Concrete Ingredients

Cement – Cement manufacturing process, steps to reduce carbon footprint, chemical composition and their importance, hydration of cement, types of cement. Testing of cement.

Fine aggregate: Functions, requirement, Alternatives to River sand, M-sand introduction and manufacturing.

Coarse aggregate: Importance of size, shape and texture. Grading and blending of aggregate. Testing on aggregate, Recycled aggregates.

Water – qualities of water.

Chemical admixtures –plasticizers, accelerators, retarders and air entraining agents.

Mineral admixtures – Pozzolanic and cementitious materials, Fly ash, GGBS, silica fumes, Met kaolin and rice husk ash. **10 Hours**

Module -2

Fresh Concrete

Workability-factors affecting workability. Measurement of workability–slump, Compaction factor and Vee-Bee Consistometer tests, flow tests. Segregation and bleeding. Process of manufacturing of concrete- Batching, Mixing, Transporting, Placing and Compaction. Curing– Methods of curing – Water curing, membrane curing, steam curing, accelerated curing, self-curing. Good and Bad practices of making and using fresh concrete and Effect of heat of hydration during mass concreting at project sites.

10 Hours

Module -3

Concrete Mix Proportioning

Concept of Mix Design with and without admixtures, variables in proportioning and Exposure conditions, Selection criteria of ingredients used for mix design, Procedure of mix proportioning. Numerical Examples of Mix Proportioning using IS-10262-2009 **10 Hours**

Module -4

Hardened Concrete Properties: Factors influencing strength, W/C ratio, gel/space ratio, Maturity concept, testing of hardened concrete, creep –factors affecting creep. Shrinkage of concrete – plastic shrinking and drying shrinkage, Factors affecting shrinkage.

Durability: Definition and significance of durability. Internal and external factors influencing durability, Mechanisms- Sulphate attack – chloride attack, carbonation, freezing and thawing. Corrosion, Durability requirements as per IS-456, In situ testing of concrete- Penetration and pull out test, Rebound hammer test, ultrasonic pulse velocity, core extraction – Principal, applications and limitations.

10 Hours

Module -5

Special Concretes

RMC- manufacture and requirement as per QCI-RMCPCS, properties, advantages and disadvantages.

Self-Compacting concrete- concept, materials, tests, properties, application and typical mix.

Fiber reinforced concrete - Fibers types, properties, application of FRC.

Light weight concrete-material properties and types. Typical lightweight concrete mix and applications

10 Hours

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

Text Books:

1. Neville A.M. “Properties of Concrete”-4th Ed., Longman.
2. M.S. Shetty, Concrete Technology - Theory and Practice Published by S. Chand and Company, New Delhi.
3. Kumar Mehta. P and Paulo J.M. Monteiro “Concrete-Microstructure, Property and Materials”, 4th Edition, McGraw Hill Education, 2014
4. A.R. Santha Kumar, “Concrete Technology”, Oxford University Press, New Delhi (New Edition)

Reference Books:

1. M L Gambir, “Concrete Technology”, McGraw Hill Education, 2014.
2. N. V. Nayak, A. K. Jain Handbook on Advanced Concrete Technology, ISBN: 978-81-8487-186-9
3. Job Thomas, “Concrete Technology”, CENGAGE Learning, 2015
4. IS 4926 (2003): Code of Practice Ready-Mixed Concrete [CED 2: Cement and Concrete]
5. Criteria for RMC Production Control, Basic Level Certification for Production Control of Ready Mixed Concrete-BMTPC
6. Specification and Guidelines for Self-Compacting Concrete, EFNARC, Association

**IV Semester B.Tech
SURVEYING II**

Sub Code : 17SCV45
Hrs/ Week : 3
Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To determine the relative position of any objects or points of the earth.
2. To determine the distance and angle between different objects.
3. To prepare a map or plan to represent an area on a horizontal plan.
4. To develop methods through the knowledge of modern science and the technology and use them in the field.
5. To solve measurement problems in an optimal way.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to Prepare the survey sheet according to the method used.

CO2: Able to apply theoretical considerations in field and other engineering projects.

CO3: Able to survey the area using different methods of plane tabling and compass survey and to adjust the compass traverse graphically.

CO4: Able to record the reduced levels using various methods of levelling and measurement of horizontal; vertical angles by Theodolite.

CO5: Able to determine the location of any point horizontally and vertically using Tachometry

MODULE 1

THEODOLITE SURVEY

Theodolite and types, Fundamental axes and parts of a transit theodolite, Uses of theodolite, Temporary adjustments of a transit theodolite, Measurement of horizontal angles – Method of repetitions and reiterations, Measurements of vertical angles, Prolonging a straight line by a theodolite in adjustment and theodolite not in adjustment

10 Hours

MODULE 2

PERMANENT ADJUSTMENT OF DUMPY LEVEL AND TRANSIT THEODOLITE

Interrelationship between fundamental axes for instrument to be in adjustment and step by step procedure of obtaining permanent adjustments

10 Hours

MODULE 3

TRIGONOMETRIC LEVELING

Determination of elevation of objects when the base is accessible and inaccessible by single plane and double plane method, Distance and difference in elevation between two inaccessible objects by double plane method. Salient features of Total Station, Advantages of Total Station over conventional instruments, Application of Total Station.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

TACHEOMETRY

Basic principle, Types of tacheometric survey, tacheometric equation for horizontal line of sight and inclined line of sight in fixed hair method, Analectic lens in external focusing telescopes, Reducing the constants in internal focusing telescope, Moving hair method and tangential method, Substance bar, Beaman stadia arc.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

CURVE SETTING (Simple curves)

Curves – Necessity – Types, Simple curves, Elements, Designation of curves, setting out simple curves by linear methods, setting out curves by Rankines deflection angle method.

(Compound and Reverse curves)

Compound curves; Elements; Design of compound curves; Setting out of compound curves Reverse curve between two parallel straights (Equal radius and unequal radius).

(Transition and Vertical curves) Transition curves; Characteristics; Length of Transition curve; Setting out cubic Parabola and Bernoulli's Lemniscates, Vertical curves –Types – Simple numerical problems.

10Hours

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

TEXT BOOKS:

1. 'Surveying' Vol 2 and Vol 3 - B. C. Punmia, Laxmi Publications
2. 'Plane Surveying' A. M. Chandra – New age international (P) Ltd
3. 'Higher Surveying' A.M. Chandra New age international (P) Ltd

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Fundamentals of Surveying** - Milton O. Schimidt – Wong, Thomson Learning.
2. **Fundamentals of Surveying** - S.K. Roy – Prentice Hall of India
3. **Surveying**, Arther Bannister et al., Pearson Education, India

**IV Semester B.Tech
BUILDING PLANNING & DRAWING**

Sub Code : 17SCV46	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 3	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 3	Exam Marks: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To understand the fundamental principles and concepts of planning and architecture for buildings.
2. To study about different views of layout.
3. To learn the development controls covered by building bye laws and national building code for buildings.
4. To learn about stairs, steel truss and types of doors
5. To learn about the preparation of water and electrical layout

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Comprehend local building bye-laws and provisions of National Building Code in respect of building and town planning.
- CO2: Discuss various aspects of principles of planning and architecture in planning building and mass composition.
- CO3: Explain the principles of planning and design considerations to construct earthquake resistant building.
- CO4: Prepare working drawings, foundation plans and other executable drawings with proper details for residential buildings.
- CO5: Able to understand the practical experience in preparation of water supply, sanitary and electrical layouts

MODULE 1

1. To prepare geometrical drawing of component of buildings i) Stepped wall footing and isolated RCC column footing, ii) Fully paneled and flush doors, iii) Half paneled and half-glazed window, iv) RCC dog legged and open well stairs, v) Steel truss.

15 Hours
2. Functional design of building (Residential, Public and Industrial), positioning of various components of buildings, orientation of buildings, building standards, bye laws, set back distances and calculation of carpet area, plinth area and floor area ratio.

10 Hours
3. Functional design of building using inter connectivity diagrams (bubble diagram), development of line diagram only for following building i) Primary health center, ii) Primary school building, iii) College canteen iv) Office building

12 Hours
4. For a given single line diagram, preparation of water supply, sanitary and electrical layouts

6 Hours

MODULE 2

5. Development of plan, elevation, section and schedule of openings from the given line diagram of residential buildings, i) Two bedroom building, ii) Two storeyed building.

27 Hours

Scheme of Examination:

Compulsory question from Module 2 for 30 marks

Plan10

Section/Elevation..... 15

Schedule of opening.....5

From Module 1 four questions should be set, out of which two have to be answered (2 x 10 = 20 marks)

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1 **“Building Drawing”**, Shah M.H and Kale C.M, Tata Mc Graw Hill Publishing co. Ltd., New Delhi.

2 **“Building Construction”**, Gurucharan Singh, Standard Publishers & distributors, New Delhi.

3 **National Building Code**, BIS, New Delhi.

IV Semester B.Tech
SURVEYING PRACTICE II

Sub Code : 17SCVL47
Hrs/ Week : 2L+1T
Credits : 2

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 3
Exam Marks: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To determine the relative position of any objects or points of the earth.
2. To determine the distance and angle between different objects.
3. To prepare a map or plan to represent an area on a horizontal plan.
4. To develop methods through the knowledge of modern science and the technology and use them in the field.
5. To solve measurement problems in an optimal way.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to Prepare the survey sheet according to the method used.

CO2: Able to apply theoretical considerations in field and other engineering projects.

CO3: Able to survey the area using different methods of double plane method and compass survey and to adjust the compass traverse graphically.

CO4: Able to record the reduced levels using various methods of levelling and measurement of horizontal; vertical angles by Theodolite.

CO5: Able to determine the location of any point horizontally and vertically using Tachometry

EXPERIMENTS

1: Measurement of horizontal angles with method of repetition and reiteration using theodolite, Measurement of vertical angles using theodolite.

2. To determine the elevation of an object using single plane method when basis accessible and inaccessible.

3. To determine the distance and difference in elevation between two inaccessible points using double plane method.

4. To determine the tacheometric constants using horizontal and inclined line of sight.

5. To set out simple curves using linear methods – perpendicular offsets from long chord and offsets from chords produced.

6. To set out simple curves using Rankine's deflection angles method.

7. To set out compound curve with angular methods with using theodolite only.

8. To set out the center line of a simple rectangular room using offset from baseline

9. To set out center lines of columns of a building using two base lines at right angles

Demonstration

Exposure to use of Total Station. Traversing, Longitudinal sections, Block levelling, Usage of relevant softwares for preparation of the contour drawings.

Scheme of Examination:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

TEXT BOOKS:

1. 'Surveying' Vol 2 and Vol 3 - B. C. Punmia, Laxmi Publications
2. 'Plane Surveying' A. M. Chandra – New age international (P) Ltd
3. 'Higher Surveying' A.M. Chandra New age international (P) Ltd

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Fundamentals of Surveying** - Milton O. Schmidt – Wong, Thomson Learning.
2. **Fundamentals of Surveying** - S.K. Roy – Prentice Hall of India
3. **Surveying**, Arther Bannister et al., Pearson Education, India

IV Semester B.Tech

APPLIED ENGINEERING GEOLOGY LABORATORY

Sub Code :	17SCVL48	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	2L+1T	Exam Hours :	3
Credits :	2	Exam Marks:	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. At the end of this course the students will be able to understand the physical and chemical properties of the Minerals
2. At the end of this course the students will be able to understand the physical and chemical properties of Rocks.
3. To understand the thickness of the beds, dip and strike of beds, and borehole problems
4. Based on this, civil engineers can choose the types of foundations and other related aspects.
5. Interpret the knowledge of geological maps for various sites.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to understand the importance and uses of minerals.

CO2: Able to understand the importance and uses of rocks and engineering uses.

CO3: Able to understand the interpretation of geological maps and their Civil Engineering structures.

CO4: Able to understand various techniques to analyze and to make possible solutions for various Geological Engineering problems.

CO5: Able to find out dip and strike of the geological formation to select suitable site.

EXPERIMENTS

1. Describe and identify the minerals based on their physical, special properties, chemical composition and uses. Study of important rock forming minerals.
2. Describe and identify the rocks as per their by giving their physical properties and engineering uses.
3. Study of Geological maps and their sections: interpreting them in terms of selecting the sites for various civil engineering structures
4. Dip and strike (surface method) problems: To find out the dip and strike of the geological formation to select suitable site for civil engineering structures.
5. Borehole problems (sub surface dip and strike): three point level ground methods.
6. Thickness of strata (out crops) problems: To determine the true thickness, vertical thickness and the width of the out crops on different topographical terrain.
7. Filed visit to Civil engineering projects –Dams, Reservoirs, Harbours etc.

Scheme of Examination:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

References books:

1. Text book of Geology by P.K. Mukerjee, World Press Pvt. Ltd. Kolkatta.
1. Foundations of Engineering Geology, by Tony Waltham (3rdEd.) Universities Press.
2. Structural Geology (3rd Ed.) by M. P. Billings, Published by Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi
3. Text of Engineering and General Geology by Parbin Singh, Published by S. K. Kataria and Sons, New Delhi.
4. Rock Mechanics for Engineers by Dr B.P.Verma, Khanna Publishers, New Delhi.
5. Engineering Geology for Civil Engineering by D. Venkata Reddy, Oxford and IBH Publishing Company, New Delhi.
6. Ground water geology by Todd D.K. John Wiley and Sons, New York.
7. Remote sensing Geology by Ravi P Gupta, Springer Verilag, New York.
8. Physical Geology by Arthur Holmes, Thomson Nelson and Sons, London.
9. Environmental Geology by K. S. Valdiya, Tata Mc GrawHills.
10. A text book of Engineering Geology by Chenna Kesavulu, Mac Millan India Ltd.
11. Remote sensing and GIS by M. Anji Reddy.
12. Ground water assessment, development and management by K.R. Karanth, Tata Mc Graw Hills

V Semester B.Tech
PRINCIPLES OF MANAGEMENT & ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Sub Code : 17SCV51	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 3	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 3	Exam Marks: 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To understand the scope and functional areas of management and approaches
2. Analyze nature and purpose, types of any organization
3. Outline the qualities of a successful entrepreneur
4. Understand the objective, scope, role of SSI in economic development
5. Identify the project and select, report with proper planning and guidance.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to understand scope and levels of management with modern management

CO2: Able to solve the problems of selection and recruitment

CO3: Able to understand the concept of entrepreneurship – evolution, development and stages of entrepreneurship.

CO4: Able to understand the policies of impact of liberalization, privatization, and globalization on SSI

CO5: Able to identify the project and select, report with proper planning and guidance.

MODULE 1

Management: Definition, Nature: Characteristics and Scope of management, functions of management, Management and administration, Levels of Management, Roles of Managers, Taylor’s Scientific Management, Henry Fayol’s administrative management, Modern Management Approaches. **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

Construction Planning, Organizing: construction stages, stages of planning, construction team, Engineering Drawings, work breakdown structure, typical construction organization. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

Scheduling and Network Diagram: Gantt chart, Schedule for various Construction Resources.

Preparation of network diagram- event and activity based and -critical path method, problems on the same. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

Entrepreneurship: Evolution of the concept, functions of an entrepreneur, Intrapreneur, SSI, stages in setting up of an SSI, Role of Entrepreneurs in the economic development, MSME

Institutional Support: Introduction to different schemes, TECKSOK, SISI, NSIC, SIDBI, KSFC
KIADB, KSSIDC, DIC **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

Business Planning Process: Project Identification, selection, project report, project appraisal and feasibility study, specimen of a project report. Making an Interviewing and preparing Mini report on any entrepreneur, and a SSI in the Civil Engineering. **10 Hours**

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

TEXT BOOKS:

1. P C Tripathi and P N Reddy, "Principles of Management", Tata McGraw-Hill Education
2. Chitkara, K.K, "Construction Project Management: Planning Scheduling and Control", Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company, New Delhi.
3. Poornima M. Charantimath , "Entrepreneurship Development and Small Business Enterprise", Dorling Kindersley (India) Pvt. Ltd., Licensees of Pearson Education
4. Dr. U.K. Shrivastava "Construction Planning and Management", Galgotia publications Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.
5. Bureau of Indian standards – IS 7272 (Part-1)- 1974 : Recommendations for labour output constant for Building works

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Robert L Peurifoy, Clifford J. Schexnayder, Aviad Shapira, Robert Schmitt, "Construction Planning, Equipment, and Methods (Civil Engineering), McGraw-Hill Education
2. Harold Koontz, Heinz Wehrich, "Essentials of Management: An International, Innovation, and Leadership perspective", T.M.H. Edition, New Delhi
3. Frank Harris, Ronald McCaffer with Francis Edum-Fotwe, "Modern Construction Management", Wiley-Blackwell
4. Mike Martin, Roland Schinzinger, "Ethics in Engineering", McGraw-Hill Education
5. Chris Hendrickson and Tung Au, "Project Management for Construction - Fundamentals Concepts for Owners, Engineers, Architects and Builders", Prentice Hall, Pittsburgh
6. James L.Riggs , David D. Bedworth , Sabah U. Randhawa " Engineerng Economics" 4 ed tata Mc Graw hill.
7. S.C Sharma –"Construction Equipments and its management" – Khanna publishers

V Semester B.Tech
DESIGN OF RCC STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS

Sub Code : 17SCV52	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 4	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 4	Exam Marks: 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. Identify, formulate and solve engineering problems of RC elements subjected to different kinds of loading.
2. Follow a procedural knowledge in designing various structural RC elements.
3. Impart the culture of following the codes for strength, serviceability and durability as an ethics.
4. Provide knowledge in analysis and design of RC elements for the success in competitive examinations.
5. To introduce the various philosophies of R.C. design and to study in detail the limit state design of structural elements such as beams, columns and footings

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Understand the design philosophy and principles.

CO2: Solve engineering problems of RC elements subjected to flexure, shear and torsion.

CO3: Demonstrate the procedural knowledge in designs of RC structural elements such as slabs, columns and footings

CO4: Able to prove the cracking in structural concrete members and its calculation

CO5: Able to understand the detailing of RC structural elements

MODULE 1

GENERAL FEATURES OF REINFORCED CONCRETE: Introduction, Design Loads, Materials for Reinforced Concrete and Code requirements. Design Philosophy – Limit State Design principles. Philosophy of limit state design, Principles of limit states, Factor of Safety, Characteristic and design loads, Characteristic and design strength. **08 Hours**

MODULE 2

PRINCIPLES OF LIMIT STATE DESIGN AND ULTIMATE STRENGTH OF R.C. SECTION:

General aspects of Ultimate strength, Stress block parameters for limit state of collapse, Ultimate flexural strength of singly reinforced rectangular sections, Ultimate flexural strength of doubly reinforced rectangular sections, Ultimate flexural strength of flanged sections, Ultimate shear strength of RC sections, Ultimate torsional strength of RC sections, Concepts of development length and anchorage, Analysis examples of singly reinforced, doubly reinforced, flanged sections, shear strength and development length. **12 Hours**

MODULE 3

DESIGN OF BEAMS: General Specification for flexure design of beams-practical requirements, size of beam, cover to reinforcement-spacing of bars. General aspects of serviceability-Deflection limits in IS: 456 – 2000. Design procedures for critical sections for moment and shears. Anchorages of bars, check for development length, Reinforcement requirements, Slenderness limits for beams to ensure lateral stability, Design examples for simply supported and Cantilever beams for rectangular and flanged sections. **10Hours**

MODULE 4

DESIGN OF SLABS: General consideration of design of slabs, Rectangular slabs spanning one direction, Rectangular slabs spanning in two directions for various boundary conditions. Design of simply supported, cantilever and continuous slabs as per IS: 456 – 2000.

DESIGN OF STAIR CASES: General features, types of stair case, loads on stair cases, effective span as per IS code provisions, distribution of loading on stairs, Design of stair cases. With waist slabs.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

DESIGN OF COLUMNS: General aspects, effective length of column, loads on columns, slenderness ratio for columns, minimum eccentricity, design of short axially loaded columns, design of column subject to combined axial load and uniaxial moment and biaxial moment using SP – 16charts.

DESIGN OF FOOTINGS: Introduction, load for footing, Design basis for limit state method, Design of isolated rectangular footing for axial load and uniaxial moment, design of pedestal.

10 Hours

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

- 1. Limit State Design of Reinforced concrete**-by P.C. Varghese, PHI Learning Private Limited 2008-2009
- 2. Fundamentals of Reinforced concrete Design**-by M.L.Gambhir, PHI Learning Private Limited 2008-2009.
- 3. Reinforced concrete Design**-by Pallai and Menon, TMH Education Private Limited,
- 4. Reinforced concrete Design**-by S.N.Shinha, TMH Education Private Limited,
- 5. Reinforced concrete Design**-by Karve & Shaha, Structures Publishers Pune.
- 6. Design of RCC Structural Elements** S. S. Bhavikatti, Vol-I, NewAge International Publications, New Delhi.
- 7. IS456: 2000 and SP16**

V Semester B.Tech
STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS – II

Sub Code : 17SCV53
Hrs/ Week : 3
Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. The course provides students with the principles of elastic structural analysis and behavior of indeterminate structures.
2. Classical and modern analysis techniques are introduced to arm the students with the necessary tools to better appreciate the real behavior of structures.
3. To analyze rigid jointed sway frames
4. To understand the structural behavior before and after application of loads.
5. Able to analyze various structure.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: To understand statically indeterminacy and adopt an appropriate structural analysis technique

CO2: Able to use slope deflection method and rotation contribution method for various civil engineering structures.

CO3: perform basic calculations to determine redundant forces and displacements, appreciate the difference between idealized structures, models and real structures.

CO4: Able to identify determinate, indeterminate, stable and unstable structures.

CO5: Possess an understanding of the physical response of structures to various loads and to identify the kinematic indeterminacy of structures.

MODULE 1

SLOPE DEFLECTION METHOD: Introduction, Sign convention, Development of slope-deflection equations and Analysis of Beams and Orthogonal Rigid jointed plane frames (non-sway) with kinematic redundancy less than/equal to three. (Members to be axially rigid)

12 Hours**MODULE 2**

MOMENT DISTRIBUTION METHOD: Introduction, Definition of terms-Distribution factor, Carry over factor, Development of method and Analysis of beams and orthogonal rigid jointed plane frames (non sway) with kinematic redundancy less than/equal to three. (Members to be axially rigid)

SWAY ANALYSIS: Analysis of rigid jointed plane frames (sway, members assumed to be axially rigid and kinematic redundancy ≤ 3) by slope deflection and moment distribution methods.

12 Hours**MODULE 3**

KANIS METHODS: Introduction, Basic Concept, Analysis of Continuous beams and Analysis of rigid jointed non-sway plane frames.

6 Hours**MODULE 4**

FLEXIBILITY MATRIX METHOD OF ANALYSIS: Introduction, Development of flexibility matrix for plane truss element and axially rigid plane framed structural elements and Analysis of plane truss and axially rigid plane frames by flexibility method with static indeterminacy.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

STIFFNESS MATRIX METHOD OF ANALYSIS: Introduction, Development of stiffness matrix for plane truss element and axially rigid plane framed structural elements. And Analysis of plane truss and axially rigid plane frames by stiffness method with kinematic indeterminacy. **10 Hours**

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Basic Structural Analysis-** Reddy C.S. - Second Edition, TataMcGraw Hill Publication Company Ltd.
2. **Theory of Structures Vol. 2** - S.P. Gupta, G.S. Pandit and R.Gupta, Tata McGraw Hill Publication Company Ltd.
3. Structural Dynamics-by M.Mukhopadhyay,
4. **Structural Analysis-II** -S. S. Bhavikatti – Vikas Publishers, NewDelhi.
5. **Basics of Structural Dynamics and Aseismic Design** ByDamodhar Swamy and Kavita PHI Learning Private Limited
6. **Structural Analysis-** D.S. Prakash Rao,, A Unified Approach,University Press
7. **Structural Analysis**, 4th SI Edition by Amit Prasanth & Aslam Kassimali, Thomson Learning.

V Semester B.Tech
GEOTECHNICAL ENGINEERING – I

Sub Code : 17SCV54	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 3	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 3	Exam Marks: 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To explain what Geotechnical Engineering is and how it is important to civil engineering
2. To explain how three phase system is used in soil and how are soil properties estimated using three phase system
3. To explain role of water in soil behavior and how soil stresses, permeability and quantity of seepage including flow net are estimated
4. To determine shear parameters and stress changes in soil due to foundation loads
5. To estimate the magnitude and time-rate of settlement due to consolidation

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: To understand the origin of soil and to identify different types of soil and apply the knowledge of soil and rock to judge its behavior and suitability for civil engineering structures.
- CO2: Able to describe Darcy's law for the flow of water through saturated soils; determine the coefficient of permeability and equivalent hydraulic conductivity in stratified soil.
- CO3: To understand the various physical and engineering characteristics of different types of soil.
- CO4: Able to calculate seepage, pore water pressure distribution, uplift forces and seepage stresses for simple geotechnical systems.
- CO5 Able to describe the direct shear test method and concept of slope stability structures.

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION: History of soil mechanics, Definition, origin and formation of soil. Phase Diagram, Voids ratio, Porosity, Percentage Air Voids, Air content, Degree of saturation, Water content, Specific Gravity of soil solids and soil mass, Densities and Unit weights - Bulk, Dry, Saturated & Submerged and their inter relationships.

INDEX PROPERTIES OF SOIL AND THEIR DETERMINATION: Index Properties of soil- Water content, Specific Gravity, Particle size distribution, Relative Density, Consistency limits and indices, in-situ density, Activity of Clay, Laboratory methods of determination of index properties of soil: Water content (Oven Drying method & Rapid Moisture method), Specific gravity of soil solids (Pycnometer and density bottle method), Particle size distribution (Sieve analysis and Hydrometer analysis only), Liquid Limit- (Casagrande and Cone penetration methods), Plastic limit and shrinkage limit.

12 Hours**MODULE 2**

CLASSIFICATION OF SOILS: Purpose of soil classification, Particle size classification – MIT classification and IS classification, Textural classification. IS classification - Plasticity chart and its importance, Field identification of soils.

CLAY MINERALOGY AND SOIL STRUCTURE: Single grained, honeycombed, flocculent and dispersed structures, Valence bonds, Soil-Water system, Electrical diffuse double layer, adsorbed water, base-exchange capacity, Isomorphous substitution. Common clay minerals in soil and their structures- Kaolinite, Illite and Montmorillonite.

8 Hours

MODULE 3

FLOW OF WATER THROUGH SOILS: Darcy's law- assumption and validity, coefficient of permeability and its determination (laboratory and field), factors affecting permeability, permeability of stratified soils, Seepage velocity, Superficial velocity and coefficient of percolation, quick sand phenomena, Capillary Phenomena.

SHEAR STRENGTH OF SOIL: Concept of shear strength, Mohr-coulomb theory, conventional and modified failure envelopes, Effective stress concept total stress, effective stress and Neutral stress, Concept of pore pressure, total and effective shear strength parameters, factors affecting shear strength of soils, Sensitivity and Thixotropy of clay.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

COMPACTION OF SOIL: Definition, Principle of compaction, Standard and Modified proctor's compaction tests, factors affecting compaction, effect of compaction on soil properties, Field compaction control – compactive effort & method, lift thickness and number of passes, Proctor's needle, Compacting equipment.

CONSOLIDATION OF SOIL: Definition, Mass-spring analogy, Terzaghi's one dimensional consolidation theory-assumption and limitations (no derivation), normally consolidated, under consolidated and over consolidated soils, pre-consolidation pressure and its determination by Casagrande's method. Consolidation characteristics of soil (C_c , a_v , m_v and C_v).

10 Hours

MODULE 5

DETERMINATION OF SHEAR STRENGTH AND CONSOLIDATION OF SOIL: Measurement of shear parameters- Direct shear test, unconfined compression test, triaxial compression test and vane shear test, Test under different drainage conditions. Laboratory one dimensional consolidation test, Determination of consolidation characteristics of soils-compression index and coefficient of consolidation (square root of time fitting method, logarithmic time fitting method).

10 Hours

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engg.**-Punmia B.C. (2005), 16thEdition Laxmi Publications Co., New Delhi.
2. **Principles of Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering**-Murthy V.N.S. (1996), 4th Edition, UBS Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi.

V Semester B.Tech**HYDROLOGY AND IRRIGATION ENGINEERING**

Sub Code :	17SCV55	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	3	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours :	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To study occurrence, movement and distribution of water which is a prime resource for development of a civilization.
2. To know diverse methods of collecting the hydrological information, which is essential, to understand surface and ground water hydrology.
3. To know the basic principles and movement of ground water and properties of ground water flow
4. To know the estimation of floods and flood droughting
5. To know the environment impact and the systems of irrigation.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1 Able to understand various techniques and parameters of irrigation.

CO2: Apply science and engineering fundamentals to solve current problems and to anticipate, mitigate and prevent future problems in the area of water resources management.

CO3: Able to know the losses of water and factors affecting

CO4: Systematic understanding of the nature of hydrological stores and fluxes and a critical awareness of the methods used to measure, analyze and forecast their variability; and the appropriate contexts for their application

CO5: To know irrigation efficiencies, assessment of water requirements for crops.

MODULE 1**INTRODUCTION TO HYDROLOGY**

Introduction, Hydrologic cycle (Horton's representation). Water budget equation Precipitation: introduction, forms and types of precipitation, measurement of precipitation (Simon's gauge & Syphon gauge only), selection of rain gauge station. Adequacy of rain gauges, methods of computing average rainfall, interpolation of missing data, double mass curve method. Hyetograph and mass curve of rainfall. Evaporation: Definition, factors affecting, measurement (Class A pan). Estimation using empirical methods (Meyer's and Rohwer's equation), evaporation control. Evapo-transpiration: Definition, factors affecting, measurement, estimation (Blaney criddle method) Infiltration: Definition, factors affecting, measurement (double ring infiltrometer), infiltration indices, and Horton's equation of infiltration.

10 Hours**MODULE 2****HYDROGRAPHS**

Definition, components of hydrographs, unit hydrograph and its derivation from simple storm hydrograph, base flow separation, Prepositions of unit hydrograph- problems

ESTIMATION OF FLOOD & FLOOD ROUTING

Definition of flood, factors affecting flood, methods of estimation (envelope curves, empirical formulae, rational method). Flood routing: Introduction to hydrological routing, relationship of out flow and storage, general storage equation, Musking umrouting method.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

INTRODUCTION TO IRRIGATION

Introduction, necessity for irrigation, advantages and disadvantages of irrigation, scope for irrigation science, types of irrigation, methods of irrigation, sewage irrigation, and supplemental irrigation.

GROUND WATER: WELL IRRIGATION

Introduction, some definitions, types of aquifers, storage coefficient, tube wells, selection of suitable site for tube well, methods for drilling tube wells, open well, methods of lifting water. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

SOIL-WATER-CROP RELATIONSHIP

Introduction, physical properties of soil, soil classification, Indian soils, classes and availability of soil water, maintaining soil fertility, soil-water-plant relationship, limiting soil moisture conditions, depth and frequency of irrigation.

WATER REQUIREMENT OF CROPS

Introduction, crop seasons of India, duty, delta, base period. Relation between duty, delta and base period, factors affecting duty, Consumptive use of water, problems. Irrigation efficiencies. Assessment of irrigation water. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

CANALS

Definition, Types of canals, Alignment of canals, Design of canals by Kennedy's and Lacey's methods- Problems, drawbacks in Kennedy's theory, defects in Lacey's theory, comparison of Kennedy's and Lacey's theories, losses in canals, maintenance of irrigation channels, measurement of discharge of a canal. **10 Hours**

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Engineering Hydrology – Subramanya. K; Tata Mcgraw Hill NewDelhi-2008 (Ed)
2. Hydrology- Madan Mohan Das, Mim Mohan Das-PHILearning private Ltd. New Delhi-2009 (Ed)
3. A Text Book of Hydrology- Jayarami Reddy, Laksmi Publications, New Delhi-2007 (Ed)
4. Irrigation, water Resources and water power Engineering- P.N.Modi- standard book house, New Delhi.
5. Irrigation and Water Power Engineering-Madan MohanDas& Mimi Das Saikia; PHIL earningpvy. Ltd. New Delhi 2009 (Ed).

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Hydrology & Soil Conservation Engineering-Ghanshyam Das- PHI Learning Private Ltd., New Delhi-2009 (Ed)
2. Hydrology & Water Resources Engineering- Patra K.C.Narosa Book Distributors Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi-2008 (Ed)
3. Hydrology & Water Resources Engineering-R.K.Sharma& Sharma, Oxford and Ibh, New Delhi
4. Irrigation Engineering and Hydraulic structures- S. K.garg- Khanna Publication, New Delhi.

V Semester B.Tech
TRANSPORTATION ENGINEERING-I

Sub Code :	17SCV56	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	3	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours :	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To understand the importance of transportation and characteristics of road transport
2. To know about the history of highway development, surveys and classification of roads
3. To study about the geometric design of highways
4. To study about traffic characteristics and design of intersections
5. To know about the pavement materials and design

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Understand the properties of materials used for construction of highways and airports.
CO2: Understand the transportation characteristics, operations, design, planning, and maintenance.
CO3: Able to collect and analyze of transportation data for use in design.
CO4: Able to prepare formal reports and describing complex design procedures
CO5: Design flexible and rigid pavements as per IRC

MODULE 1

PRINCIPLES OF TRANSPORTATION ENGINEERING:

Importance of transportation, Different modes of transportation and comparison, Characteristics of road transport Jayakar committee recommendations, and implementation – Central Road Fund, Indian Roads Congress, Central Road Research Institute

HIGHWAY DEVELOPMENT AND PLANNING: Road types and classification, road patterns, planning surveys, master plan – saturation system of road planning, phasing road

Development in India, problems on best alignment among alternate proposals Salient Features of 3rd and 4th twenty year road development plans and Policies, Present scenario of road development in India (NHDP & PMGSY) and in Karnataka (KSHIP & KRDCIL) Road development plan - vision 2021.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

HIGHWAY ALIGNMENT AND SURVEYS: Ideal Alignment, Factors affecting the alignment, Engineering surveys-Map study, Reconnaissance, Preliminary and Final location & detailed survey, Reports and drawings for new and re-aligned projects

HIGHWAY GEOMETRIC DESIGN – I: Importance, Terrain classification, Design speed, Factors affecting geometric design, **Cross sectional elements**-Camber- width of pavement- Shoulders-, Width of formation- Right of way, typical cross sections.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

HIGHWAY GEOMETRIC DESIGN – II: Sight Distance-Restrictions to sight distance- Stopping sight distance-Overtaking sight distance- overtaking zones- Examples on SSD and OSD- Sight distance at intersections, **Horizontal alignment**-Radius of Curve- Super elevation – Extra widening-Transition

curve and its length, setback distance – Examples, **Vertical alignment**-Gradient-summit and valley curves with examples.

PAVEMENT MATERIALS: Subgrade soil –desirable properties-HRB soil classification-determination of CBR and modulus of subgrade reaction-Examples on CBR and Modulus of subgrade reaction, **Aggregates**- Desirable properties and list of tests. **Bituminous materials**-Explanation on Tar, Bitumen, Cutback and Emulsion-List of tests on bituminous materials

10 Hours

MODULE 4

PAVEMENT DESIGN: Pavement types, component parts of flexible and rigid pavements and their functions, design factors, ESWL and its determination-Examples, **Flexible pavement**- Design of flexible pavements as per IRC:37-2001-Examples, **Rigid pavement**- Westergaard's equations for load and temperature stresses- Examples- Design of slab thickness only as per IRC:58-2002

PAVEMENT CONSTRUCTION: Earthwork –cutting-Filling, Preparation of subgrade, Specification and construction of i) Granular Sub base, ii) WBM Base, iii) WMM base, iv) Bituminous Macadam, v) Dense Bituminous Macadam vi) Bituminous Concrete, vii) Dry Lean Concrete sub base and PQC viii) concrete roads

10 Hours

MODULE 5

HIGHWAY ECONOMICS: Highway user benefits, VOC using charts only-Examples, Economic analysis - annual cost method-Benefit Cost Ratio method-NPV-IRR methods-Examples, Highway financing-BOT-BOOT concepts

10 Hours

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Highway Engineering** – S K Khanna and C E G Justo, Nem Chand Bros, Roorkee
2. **Highway Engineering** - L R Kadiyali, Khanna Publishers, New Delhi
3. **Transportation Engineering** – K P Subramaniam, Scitech Publications, Chennai
4. **Transportation Engineering** – James H Banks, Mc.Graw. Hill Pub. New Delhi
5. **Highway Engineering** –R. Sreenivasa Kumar, University Press. Pvt. Ltd. Hyderabad

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Relevant IRC Codes
2. Specifications for Roads and Bridges – MORTH and IRC, New Delhi

V Semester B.Tech

HYDRAULICS AND HYDRAULIC MACHINES LABORATORY

Sub Code :	17SCVL57	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	2L+1T	Exam Hours :	3
Credits :	2	Exam Marks:	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To understand the flow measurement in a pipe flow
2. To determine the energy loss in pipe flow
3. To study the characteristics of turbines
4. To study the characteristics of pumps
5. To measure the discharge in an open channel flow

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Able to measure discharge in pipes
CO2: Able to determine the energy loss in conduits
CO3: Able to demonstrate the characteristics curves of pumps
CO4: Able to demonstrate the characteristics curves of turbines
CO5: To carry out discharge measurements in open channel

EXPERIMENTS

1. Calibration of pressure gauge (dead weight method)
2. Calibration of 90° V-notch
3. Calibration of Rectangular and Cipolletti notch
4. Calibration of Broad- crested weir
5. Calibration of Venturiflume
6. Calibration of Venturimeter
7. Determination of Darcy's friction factor for a straight pipe
8. Determination of Hydraulic coefficients of a vertical orifice
9. Determination of vane coefficients for a flat vane & semicircular vane
10. Performance characteristics of a single stage centrifugal pump
11. Performance characteristics of a Pelton wheel
12. Performance characteristics of a Kaplan turbine

Scheme of Examination:

- ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks
ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks
Viva – voce = 10 marks
Total: 50 marks

REFERENCE:

- Experiments in Fluid Mechanics – Sarbjit Singh- PHI Pvt. Ltd.- NewDelhi- 2009-12-30
Hydraulics and Hydraulic Machines Laboratory Manual – Dr. N. Balasubramanya

V Semester B.Tech
COMPUTER AIDED DESIGN LABORATORY

Sub Code : 17SCVL58	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 2L+1T	Exam Hours : 3
Credits : 2	Exam Marks: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To learn the programming of numerical methods
2. To use the computer to apply numerical techniques
3. To learn the fundamentals of Computer Aided Drafting
4. To understand Civil Engineering Drawing concepts
5. To learn the handling of spreadsheets

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Able to develop programs for numerical methods
 CO2: Able to solve numerical techniques in computer
 CO3: Able to implement Computer Aided Drafting
 CO4: Able to apply Building concepts to Civil Engineering
 CO5: Able to apply Spreadsheet calculations to Civil Engineering

1. AUTOCAD**1.1 Basics of AUTOCAD:**

DRAWING TOOLS: Lines, Circle, Arc, Polyline, Multiline, Polygon, Rectangle, Spline, Ellipse, *Modify tools:* Erase, Copy, Mirror, Offset, Array, Move, Rotate, Scale, Stretch, Lengthen, Trim, Extend, Break, Chamfer and Fillet, *Using Text:* Single line text, Multiline text, Spelling, Edit text, Special Features: View tools, Layers concept, Dimension tools, Hatching, Customising toolbars, working with multiple drawings

3 Hours**1.2 Use of AUTOCAD in Civil Engineering Drawings:**

Following drawings are to be prepared for the data given using AUTOCAD

- i) Cross section of Foundation - masonry wall, RCC columns (isolated)
- ii) Different types of staircases
- iii) Lintel and chajja
- iv) RCC slabs and beams
- v) Drawing of Plan, elevation and sectional elevation of single storied residential and public buildings given the single line diagram and preparing excavation plan.

18 Hours**2. STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS SOFTWARE**

Use of commercially available software for the analysis of

- i) Plane Trusses
- ii) Continuous beams
- iii) 2D Portal frames-single storied and multistoried

9Hours

3. USE OF EXCEL IN CIVIL ENGINEERING PROBLEMS

Use of spread sheet for the following civil engineering problems

- i) SFD and BMD for Cantilever and simply supported beam subjected to uniformly distributed and uniformly varying load acting throughout the span
- ii) Design of singly reinforced and doubly reinforced rectangular beams
- iii) Computation of earthwork
- iv) Design of horizontal curve by offset method
- v) Design of super elevation

12 Hours

Scheme of Examination:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Computer Aided Design Laborator-** Dr M.N.Shesha Prakash,Dr.G.S.Suresh, Lakshmi Publications
2. **CAD Laboratory-** M.A.Jayaram, D.S.Rajendra Prasad- SapnaPublications
3. **AUTOCAD 2002-** Roberts JT, -BPB publications
4. **AUTOCAD 2004-** Sham Tickoo, A beginner's Guide, WileyDreamtech India Pvt Ltd.,
5. **Learning Excel 2002-** Ramesh Bangia, -Khanna Book PublishingCo (P) Ltd.,
6. **Microsoft Excel-** Mathieson SA, Starfire publishers

VI Semester B.Tech
ENVIRONMENTAL ENGINEERING-I

Sub Code : 17SCV61	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 4	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 4	Exam Marks: 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To make the students conversant with sources and its demand of water
2. To understand the basic characteristics of water and its determination
3. To expose the students to understand the design of water supply lines
4. To provide adequate knowledge about the water treatment processes and its design
5. To have adequate knowledge on operation and maintenance of water supply

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to identify the source of water and water demand

CO2: Able to apply the water treatment concept and methods

CO3: Able to apply water distribution processes and operation and maintenance of water supply

CO4: Able to prepare basic process designs of water and wastewater treatment plants collect, reduce

CO5: Able to analyze and evaluate basic water quality data

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION: Human activities and environmental pollution. Water for various beneficial uses and quality requirement. Need for protected water supply.

DEMAND OF WATER: Types of water demands- domestic demand in detail, institutional and commercial, public uses, fire demand. Per capita consumption –factors affecting per capita demand, population forecasting, different methods with merits &demerits- variations in demand of water. Fire demand – estimation by Kuichling’s formula, Freeman formula & National Board of Fire Under writers formula, peak factors, design periods & factors governing the design periods

SOURCES: Surface and subsurface sources – suitability with regard to quality and quantity.

10 Hours**MODULE 2**

COLLECTION AND CONVEYANCE OF WATER: Intake structures –different types of intakes; factor of selection and location of intakes. Pumps- Necessity, types – power of pumps; factors for the selection of a pump. Pipes – Design of the economical diameter for the rising main; Nomograms – use; Pipe appurtenances.

QUALITY OF WATER: Objectives of water quality management. Wholesomeness & palatability, water borne diseases. Water quality parameters – Physical, chemical and Microbiological. Sampling of water for examination. Water quality analysis (IS: 3025 and IS: 1622) using analytical and instrumental techniques. Drinking water standards BIS & WHO guidelines. Health significance of Fluoride, Nitrates and heavy metals like Mercury, Cadmium, Arsenic etc. and toxic / trace organics.

10 Hours**MODULE 3**

WATER TREATMENT: Objectives – Treatment flow-chart. Aeration- principles.

SEDIMENTATION: Theory, settling tanks, types, design. Coagulant aided sedimentation, jar test, chemical feeding, flash mixing, and clariflocculator.

FILTRATION: Mechanism – theory of filtration, types of filters, slow sand, rapid sand and pressure filters including construction, operation, cleaning and their design – excluding under drainage system – backwashing of filters. Operational problems in filters.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

DISINFECTION: Theory of disinfection, types of disinfection, Chlorination, chlorine demand, residual chlorine, use of bleaching powder. UV irradiation treatment – treatment of swimming pool water

SOFTENING – definition, methods of removal of hardness by lime soda process and zeolite process RO & Membrane technique.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

MISCELLANEOUS TREATMENT: Removal of color, odor, taste, use of copper sulfate, adsorption technique, fluoridation and defluoridation.

DISTRIBUTION SYSTEMS: System of supply, service reservoirs and their capacity determination, methods of layout of distribution systems.

MISCELLANEOUS: Pipe appurtenances, various valves, type of fire hydrants, pipefitting, Layout of water supply pipes in buildings.

10 Hours

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Water supply Engineering –S.K. Garg, Khanna Publishers
2. Environmental Engineering I –B C Punima and Ashok Jain
3. Manual on Water supply and treatment –CPHEEO, Ministry of Urban Development, New Delhi

REFERENCES

1. Hammer, M.J., (1986), **Water and Wastewater Technology** –SI Version, 2nd Edition, John Wiley and Sons.
2. Karia, G.L., and Christian, R.A., (2006), **Wastewater Treatment –Concepts and Design Approach**, Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
3. Metcalf and Eddy, (2003), **Wastewater Engineering, Treatment and Reuse**, 4th Edition, Tata McGraw Hill Edition, Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Co. Ltd.
4. Peavy, H.S., Rowe, D.R., and Tchobanoglous, G.,(1986),**Environmental Engineering**–Mc Graw Hill Book Co.
5. Raju, B.S.N., (1995), **Water Supply and Wastewater Engineering**, Tata McGraw Hill Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
6. Sincero, A.P., and Sincero, G.A., (1999), **Environmental Engineering – A Design Approach**–Prentice Hall of India Pvt.Ltd., New Delhi.

VI Semester B.Tech
DESIGN & DRAWING OF RC STRUCTURES

Sub Code :	17SCV62	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	3	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours :	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To study the stress strain behavior of steel and concrete
2. To understand the concept of working stress and limit state methods
3. To gain the knowledge of limit state design for flexure, shear, torsion, bond and anchorage
4. To understand the behavior of columns subjected to eccentric load and use of interaction diagrams
5. To study the design of various foundation

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1 Able to describe about composition and characteristics of Portland cement.

CO2 Able to classify the aggregate and their various properties.

CO3 Able to identify the various properties of concrete and analyzing its workability.

CO4 Able to illustrate design philosophies.

CO5 Able to solve problems in context to singly, doubly and flanged Beam.

MODULE 1

1. Layout Drawing: General layout of building showing, position of columns, footings, beams and slabs with standard notations.
2. Detailing of Beam and Slab floor system, continuous beams.
3. Detailing of Staircases: Dog legged and Open well.
4. Detailing of Column footings: Column and footing (Square and Rectangle)

25 HOURS

MODULE 2

1. Design and detailing of Rectangular Combined footing slab and beam type
2. Design and detailing of Retaining walls (Cantilever and counter fort type)
3. Design and detailing of Circular and Rectangular water tanks resting on ground and free at top (Flexible base and Rigid base), using IS: 3370 (Part IV) only.
4. Design and detailing of Simple Portal Frames subjected to gravity loads.(Single bay & Single storey)

25 HOURS

Scheme of Examination:

Answer any one full question from each module. Each module carries equal marks (2 x 25 = 50 marks)

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Structural Design & Drawing Reinforced Concrete & Steel-** N. Krishnaraju, University Press.
2. **Structural Design and Drawing-** Krishnamurthy -, (Concrete Structures), CBS publishers, New Delhi. Tata Mc-Graw publishers.
3. **Reinforced Concrete Structures** - B.C. Punmia – Laxmi Publishing Co.
4. **Reinforced Concrete Design** – S.N.Sinha, Mc Graw Hill Education,

VI Semester B.Tech
TRANSPORTATION ENGINEERING-II

Sub Code : 17SCV63	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 3	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 3	Exam Marks : 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To know about the basics and design of various components of railway engineering
2. To study about the types and functions of track, junctions and railway stations
3. To learn about the aircraft characteristics, planning and components of airport
4. To study about the types and components of docks and harbours
5. To know about various urban transportation systems and Intelligent Transportation Systems

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to carry out the surveys for railways, airports and harbours

CO2: Able to perform geometric design for the three modes

CO3: Able to plan the layout of different types of terminals

CO4: Able to apply the principles of bus transit, MRTS and LRT

CO5: Able to demonstrate the fundamentals of Intelligent Transportation Systems

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION: Role of railways in transportation, Indian Railways, Selection of Routes, Permanent way and its requirements, Gauges and types, Typical cross sections-single and double line B G track in cutting, embankment and electrified tracks, Coning of wheels and tilting of rails, **Rails**-Functions-requirements—types and sections length-defects-wear-creep-welding-joints, creep of rails

SLEEPERS AND BALLAST: Functions, requirements, Types, Track fitting and fasteners-Dog spike, screw spike and Pandrol clip,-Fishplates-bearing plates, Calculation of quantity of materials required for laying a track-Examples, **Tractive resistances** and hauling capacity with examples

10 Hours**MODULE 2**

GEOMETRIC DESIGN: Necessity, Safe speed on curves, **Cant**-cant deficiency-negative cant-safe speed based on various criteria,(both for normal and high speed tracks) Transition curve, Gradient and types, grade compensation, Examples on above.

POINTS AND CROSSING: Components of a turnout, Details of Points and Crossing, Design of turnouts with examples (No derivations) types of switches, crossings, track junctions Stations and Types, Types of yards, Signalling-Objects and types of signals, station and yard Equipment-Turn table, Fouling mark, buffer stop, level crossing, track defects, and maintenance.

10 Hours**MODULE 3**

INTRODUCTION: Layout of an airport with component parts and functions, Site selection for airport, Aircraft characteristics affecting the design and planning of airport, Airport classification, Runway orientation using wind rose with examples

RUNWAY- Basic runway length-Corrections and examples, Runway geometrics, **Taxiway**-Factors affecting the layout - geometrics of taxiway-Design of exit taxiway with examples, **Visual aids-** Airport marking – lighting-Instrumental Landing System.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

TUNNELS: Advantages and disadvantages, Size and shape of tunnels, Surveying-Transferring centre line, and gradient from surface to inside the tunnel working face, Weisbach triangle-Examples, Tunnelling in rocks-methods, Tunnelling methods in soils-Needle beam, Liner plate, Tunnel lining, Tunnel ventilation, vertical shafts, Pilot tunneling, mucking and methods, drilling and drilling pattern.
10 Hours

MODULE 5

HARBOURS: Harbour classifications, Layout with components, Natural phenomenon affecting the design of harbours - wind, waven and tide, currents, Breakwater-Types Wharf and Quays, Jetties and Piers, Dry dock and wet docks, Slipways, Navigational aids, warehouse and transit-shed.

10 Hours

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

TEXT BOOKS

- 1. Railway Engineering** - Saxena and Arora, Dhanpat Rai & Sons, New Delhi
- 2. Indian Railway Track** – M M Agarwal, Jaico Publications, Bombay
- 3. Airport Planning and Design** – Khanna Arora and Jain, NemChand Bros, Roorkee
- 4. Doks and Tunnel Engineering** – R Srinivasan, Charaotar Publishing House
- 5. Docks and Harbour Engineering** –H P Oza and G H OzaCharaotar Publishing House
- 6. Surveying** – B C Punmia, Laxmi Publications

VI Semester B.Tech
PROFESSIONAL ELECTIVE A -1
GEOTECHNICAL ENGINEERING – II

Sub Code : 17SCV641	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 3	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 3	Exam Marks: 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To emphasize the importance of soil investigations including destructive and nondestructive methods
2. To explain how earth pressure theory is important in retaining structure design
3. To explain the concept of bearing capacity and how to estimate the safe bearing capacity for various foundation system including settlement consideration
4. To explain how do select a suitable shallow foundation system for various site conditions and also analysis of different foundation system
5. To explain in what circumstances pile is needed and how do analysis the pile and pile group under various soil conditions

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to carry out soil investigation for any civil engineering construction

CO2: Able to analyze earth retaining structures for any kind of soil medium

CO3: Able to estimate bearing capacity using IS code methods

CO4: Able to design proper foundations for any kind of shallow foundation system

CO5: Able to estimate pile and pile group capacity for any kind of soil including group efficiency and negative friction

MODULE 1

SUBSURFACE EXPLORATION: Importance of exploration program, Methods of exploration: Boring, Seismic refraction method of geophysical exploration, Types of samples - Undisturbed, disturbed and representative samples, Samplers, sample disturbance, area ratio, Recovery ratio, clearance, Stabilization of boreholes - Typical bore log. Number and depth of borings for various civil engineering structures, soil exploration report.

DRAINAGE AND DEWATERING: Determination of groundwater level by Hvorslev's method, Control of ground water during excavation: Dewatering - Ditches and sumps, well point system, Vacuum method, Electro- Osmosis method.

10 Hours**MODULE 2**

STRESSES IN SOILS: Boussinesq's and Westergaard's theories for concentrated, circular and rectangular loads. Comparison of Boussinesq's and westergaard's analysis. Pressure distribution diagrams, Contact pressure, Newmark's chart.

FLOWNETS: Laplace equation (no derivation) assumptions and limitations only, characteristics and uses of flownets, Methods of drawing flownets for Dams and sheet piles. Estimating quantity of seepage and Exit gradient. Determination of phreatic line in earth dams with and without filter. Piping and protective filter.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

LATERAL EARTH PRESSURE: Active and passive earth pressures, Earth pressure at rest. Rankine's and Coulomb's Earth pressure theories—assumptions and limitations, Graphical solutions for active earth pressure (cohesionless soil only) – Culmann's and Rebhann's methods, Lateral earth pressure in cohesive and cohesion less soils, Earth pressure distribution.

STABILITY OF EARTH SLOPES: Types of slopes, causes and type of failure of slopes. Definition of factor of safety, Stability of infinite slopes, Stability of finite slopes by Method of slices and Friction Circle method, Taylor's stability number, Fellenius method. **12 Hours**

MODULE 4

BEARING CAPACITY: Definitions of ultimate, net and safe bearing capacities, Allowable bearing pressure. Terzaghi's and Brinch Hansen's bearing capacity equations -assumptions and limitations, Bearing capacity of footing subjected to eccentric loading. Effect of ground water table on bearing capacity. Field methods of evaluation of bearing capacity - Plate load test, Standard penetration test and cone penetration test. **8 Hours**

MODULE 5

FOUNDATION SETTLEMENT: Importance and Concept of Settlement Analysis, Immediate, Consolidation and Secondary settlements (no derivations, but, computation using relevant formula for Normally Consolidated soils), Tolerance. BIS specifications for total and differential settlements of footings and rafts.

PROPORTIONING SHALLOW AND PILE FOUNDATIONS

Allowable Bearing Pressure, Factors influencing the selection of depth of foundation, Factors influencing Allowable Bearing Pressure, Factors influencing the choice of foundation, Proportioning isolated, combined, strip and mat foundations, Classification of pile foundation, Pile load capacity, Proportioning pile foundation. **10 Hours**

Scheme of Examination:

Two questions to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Soil Engineering in Theory and Practice-** Alam Singh and Chowdhary G.R. (1994), CBS Publishers and Distributors Ltd., New Delhi.
2. **Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engg.-**Punmia B.C. (2005), 16th Edition Laxmi Publications Co., New Delhi.

REFERENCES BOOKS:

1. **Foundation Analysis and Design-** Bowles J.E. (1996), 5th Edition, McGraw Hill Pub. Co. New York.
2. **Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering-** Murthy V.N.S. (1996), 4th Edition, UBS Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi.
3. **Basic and Applied Soil Mechanics-** Gopal Ranjan and Rao A.S.R. (2000), New Age International (P) Ltd., New Delhi.
4. **Geotechnical Engineering-** Venkatrahmaiah C. (2006), 3rd Edition New Age International (P) Ltd.
5. **Soil Mechanics-** Craig R.F. (1987), Van Nostrand Reinhold Co. Ltd.
6. **Principles of Geotechnical Engineering-** Braja M. Das (2002), 5th Edition, Thomson Business Information India (P) Ltd., India.
7. **Text Book of Geotechnical Engineering-** Iqbal H. Khan (2005), 2nd Edition, PHI, India.

VI Semester B.Tech
PROFESSIONAL ELECTIVE A -2
URBAN TRANSPORT PLANNING

Sub Code :	17SCV642	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	3	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours :	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To know about the process and concepts of transportation planning
2. To study about trip generation
3. To study about trip distribution
4. To study about modal split analysis
5. To study about trip assignment

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Apply the principles of the transportation planning process and demand estimation
CO2: Analyze the trip production and trip attraction models
CO3: Analyze the growth factor, gravity and opportunity models
CO4: Apply the mode choice behavior and mode split models
CO5: Apply the shortest path models for route assignment

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION: Scope of Urban transport planning – Inter dependency of land use and traffic – System Approach to urban planning.

STAGES IN URBAN TRANSPORT PLANNING: Trip generation – Trip production - Trip distribution – Modal split – Trip assignment. **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

URBAN TRANSPORT SURVEY - Definition of study area-Zoning-Types of Surveys – Inventory of transportation facilities – Expansion of data from sample. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

TRIP GENERATION: Trip purpose – Factors governing trip generation and attraction – Category analysis – Problems on above

TRIP DISTRIBUTION: Methods – Growth factors methods – Synthetic methods – Fractor and Furness method and problems on the above. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

MODAL SPLIT: Factors affecting – characteristics of split – Model split inurban transport planning – problems on above

TRIP ASSIGNMENT: Assignment Techniques – Traffic fore casting –Land use transport models – Lowry Model – Garin Lowry model –Applications in India – (No problems on the above). **12 Hours**

MODULE 5

URBAN TRANSPORT PLANNING FOR SMALL AND MEDIUMCITIES: Introduction – Difficulties in transport planning – Recent Case Studies. **8 Hours**

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Traffic Engineering and Transport Planning-** L.R. Kadiyali -Khanna Publishers.
2. **Principles of urban transport system planning** - B.G. Hutchinson- Scripta Book Co., Washington D.C. & McGraw Hill Book Co.
3. **Introduction to transportation engineering-** JotinKristey and Kentlal - PHI, New Delhi.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Urban Transport planning-** Black John - Croom Helm ltd, London.
2. **Urban and Regional models in geography and planning-**Hutchison B G - John Wiley and sons London.
3. **Entropy in urban and regional modeling-** Wilson A G - Pion ltd, London.

VI Semester B.Tech
PROFESSIONAL ELECTIVE A -3
STRUCTURAL DYNAMICS

Sub Code : 17SCV643	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 3	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 3	Exam Marks: 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To introduce the concepts of dynamic systems
2. To study the dynamic response of SDOF
3. To study the dynamic response of MDOF
4. To introduce the continuous systems subjected to different types of dynamic loads
5. To learn free and forced vibrations response of structural systems

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: To apply the concepts of dynamic systems

CO2: To identify, formulate and solve dynamic response of SDOF

CO3: To identify, formulate and solve dynamic response of MDOF

CO4: To analyze continuous systems subjected to different types of dynamic loads

CO5: To identify, formulate and solve free and forced vibrations response of structural systems

MODULE 1

Introduction: Introduction to Dynamic problems in Civil Engineering, Concept of degrees of freedom, D'Alembert's principle, principle of virtual displacement and energy principles Dynamics of Single-degree-of-freedom systems: Mathematical models of Single-degree-of-freedom systems system, Free vibration response of damped and undamped systems. Methods of evaluation of damping. **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

Response of Single-degree-of-freedom systems to harmonic loading (rotation unbalance, reciprocating unbalance) including support motion, vibration isolation, transmissibility, Numerical methods applied to Single-degree-of-freedom systems - Duhamel integral, principle of vibration-measuring instruments - seismometer and accelerometer. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

Dynamics of Multi-degree freedom systems: Mathematical models of multi-degree-of-freedom systems, Shear building concept, free vibration of undamped multi-degree-of-freedom systems - Natural frequencies and mode shapes - orthogonality property of modes. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

Response of Shear buildings for harmonic loading without damping using normal mode approach. Response of Shear buildings for forced vibration for harmonic loading with damping using normal mode approach, condition of damping uncoupling. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

Approximate methods: Rayleigh's method Dunkarley's method, Stodola's method. Dynamics of Continuous systems: Free longitudinal vibration of bars, flexural vibration of beams with different end conditions. Stiffness matrix, mass matrix (lumped and consistent); equations of motion for the discredited beam in matrix form. **10 Hours**

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Dynamics of Structures - Theory and Application to Earthquake Engineering"- 2nd ed., Anil K. Chopra, Pearson Education.
2. Earthquake Resistant Design of Building Structures, Vinod Hosur, WILEY (india)
3. Vibrations, structural dynamics- M. Mukhopadhaya : Oxford IBH.
4. Structural Dynamics- Mario Paz : CBS publishers.
5. Structural Dynamics- Clough & Penzien : TMH
6. Vibration Problems in Engineering Timoshenko, S, Van-Nostrand Co.

VI Semester B.Tech
PROFESSIONAL ELECTIVE B -1
GROUND IMPROVEMENT TECHNIQUES

Sub Code :	17SCV651	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	3	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours :	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. Understand the fundamental concepts of ground improvement techniques
2. Apply knowledge of mathematics, Science and Geotechnical Engineering to solve problems in the field of modification of ground required for construction of civil engineering structures.
3. Understand the concepts of chemical compaction, grouting and other miscellaneous methods.
4. Impart the knowledge of geosynthetics, vibration, grouting and Injection.
5. Educate students with numerous ground improvement principles and methods to overcome the problems related to soil on site

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Identify the problematic soil

CO2: Suggest the appropriate ground improvement technique as per the requirement of the project (dewatering, densification, stabilization, swelling control etc.)

CO3: Analyze and design the technique for ground improvement

CO4: Learn how to change the properties of soil to overcome these problems by modifying the soil and by suitable interventions with the soil.

CO5: Able to understand the types of grouts, equipment's and machinery.

MODULE 1

FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF GROUND: Introduction, Formation of Rock, soil and soil profile, Soil distribution in India, Alterations of ground after formation, Reclaimed soils, Natural offshore deposits; Ground Improvement Potential – Hazardous ground conditions, poor ground conditions, favorable ground conditions, Alternative Approaches, Geotechnical processes.

COMPACTION: Introduction, compaction mechanics, Field procedure, surface compaction, Dynamic Compaction, selection of field compaction procedures, compaction quality control.

10Hours

MODULE 2

DRAINAGE METHODS: Introduction, Seepage, filter requirements, ground water and seepage control, methods of dewatering systems, Design of dewatering system including pipe line effects of dewatering. Drains, different types of drains.

PRECOMPRESSION AND VERTICAL DRAINS: Importance, Vertical drains, Sand drains, Drainage of slopes, Electro kinetic dewatering, Preloading.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

CHEMICAL MODIFICATION-I: Definition, cement stabilization, sandwich technique, admixtures. Hydration – effect of cement stabilization on permeability, Swelling and shrinkage and strength and deformation characteristics. Criteria for cement stabilization. Stabilization using Fly ash.

CHEMICAL MODIFICATION-II: Lime stabilization – suitability, process, criteria for lime stabilization. Other chemicals like chlorides, hydroxides, lignin and hydrofluoric acid. Properties of chemical components, reactions and effects. Bitumen, tar or asphalt in stabilization.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

VIBRATION METHODS: Introduction, Vibro compaction– blasting, vibratory probe, Vibro displacement compaction – displacement piles, vibro flotation, sand compaction piles, stone columns, heavy tamping

GROUTING AND INJECTION: Introduction, Effect of grouting. Chemicals and materials used. Types of grouting. Grouting procedure, Applications of grouting

10 Hours

MODULE 5

GEOSYNTHETICS: Introduction, Geosynthetic types, properties of Geosynthetics – materials and fibre properties, Geometrical aspects, mechanical properties, Hydraulic properties, Durability ; Applications of Geosynthetics - Separation, Filtration and Fluid Transmission, Reinforcement,

MISCELLANEOUS METHODS (ONLY CONCEPTS & USES): Soil reinforcement, Thermal methods, Ground improvement by confinement – Crib walls, Gabions and Mattresses, Anchors, Rock bolts and soil nailing. Stone Column, Micro piles

10 Hours

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Ground Improvement Techniques-** Purushothama Raj P.(1999) Laxmi Publications, New Delhi.
2. **Construction and Geotechnical Method in Foundation Engineering-** Koerner R.M. (1985) - Mc Graw Hill Pub. Co.,New York.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Engineering principles of ground modification-** Manfred Hausmann (1990) - Mc Graw Hill Pub. Co., New York.
2. **Methods of treatment of unstable ground-** Bell, F.G. (1975) Butterworths, London.
3. **Expansive soils-** Nelson J.D. and Miller D.J. (1992) -, John Wiley and Sons.
4. **Soil Stabilization; Principles and Practice-** Ingles. C.G. and Metcalf J.B. (1972) - Butterworths, London.

VI Semester B.Tech
PROFESSIONAL ELECTIVE B -2
PRINCIPLES OF CONSTRUCTION MANAGEMENT

Sub Code :	17SCV652	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	3	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours :	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. Understand the broad principles and concepts of construction management
2. To create awareness of MCM techniques in construction industry
3. Represent various works measurement standards
4. Understand the quality and safety management
5. Estimate the cost and government policies of infrastructure.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Ability to take responsibilities as construction manager

CO2: Application of MCM technique in the real time construction operation

CO3: Knowledge of work measurement application in construction industry

CO4: Able to understand the safety of buildings

CO5: Able to understand the rules and regulations followed in the construction contract.

MODULE 1

CONSTRUCTION PROJECT FORMULATION: Introduction- Project Management: An Overview - Types, Project Organization; Characteristics of Projects –Project life cycle; Project Appraisal – Feasibility study; Introduction to Time value of money; Net Present Value, Benefit Cost Ratio with problems; Evaluation of Public Projects –BOOT, BOT, BOLT concepts.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

CONSTRUCTION CONTRACT: Indian Contracts Act 1872 – Basic Terminologies; Engineering contract classification, Sub contracts; CPWD – FIDIC form of contract methods; Arbitration; Tender – Basics of evaluation.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

CONSTRUCTION PLANNING & SCHEDULING: Introduction –types of project plans -work breakdown structure; Planning techniques -bar charts -preparation of network diagram; Critical Path Method Problems Program Evaluation and Review Technique with Problems; Basics of Resource Management.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

CONSTRUCTION QUALITY AND SAFETY MANAGEMENT: Construction quality -inspection, quality control and quality assurance; Total quality management -quality gurus and their teachings; ISO standards -audit -evaluation of safety - Accident causation theories -health and safety act and regulations; Role of safety personnel -causes of accidents -principles of safety -safety and health management system

10 Hours

MODULE 5

APPLICATION OF OPERATION RESEARCH TECHNIQUES IN CONSTRUCTION:

Introduction -concepts in probability and statistics; linear programming by Graphical Method-Different types of LPP Solution; Transportation Problems; Assignment Problems; Simulation Techniques-Introduction to Monte Carlo Method simulation-functions of random variables

10 Hours

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

REFERENCES

1. Kumar NeerajJha, "Construction project management", Dorling Kindersley,NewDelhi.2013
2. Sengupta .B, Guha .H, "Construction management and planning",Tata Mcgraw Hill,New Delhi,2001.
3. Sharma .S.C, "Construction engineering and management", Khanna Publishers,Delhi,2008.
4. Murugesan .G, "Total quality management", Laxmi Publications,Delhi,2013
5. Prasanna Chandra, "Planning, Analysis, Selection, Financing, Implementation, and Review", 7thEdition, Tata Mcgraw Hill,New Delhi,2001.
6. PannerSelvam, "Operation research", PHI India Private limited, New Delhi, 2011.

VI Semester B.Tech
PROFESSIONAL ELECTIVE B -3
HYDRAULIC STRUCTURES AND IRRIGATION DESIGN-DRAWING

Sub Code : 17SCV653
Hrs/ Week : 3
Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To understand the basic types of irrigation, irrigation standards and crop water assessment
2. To study the different aspects of design of hydraulic structures
3. To provide knowledge on various hydraulic structures such as energy dissipaters, head and cross regulators, canal falls and structures involved in cross drainage works
4. To understand the analysis of seepage and hydraulic jump
5. To design different types of dams

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: To assess the irrigation needs of crops
CO2: To design weirs on pervious foundation
CO3: To design gravity dam and earthen dam
CO4: To design the canal systems
CO5: To select and design canal fall

MODULE 1

Hydraulic Structures

Reservoir Planning

Introduction, classification of Reservoirs, Storage zones of a reservoir, Mass curve, fixing capacity of a reservoir, safe yield, problems, density currents, Trap efficiency, Reservoir sedimentation, life of a reservoir, economic height of a dam, problems. Environmental effects of reservoirs,

Gravity Dams

Introduction, forces on a gravity dam, stress analysis in gravity dam, Problems, combination of forces for design. Elementary & practical profiles of a gravity dam, stability analysis (without earthquake forces), problems, galleries in gravity dams,

12 Hours

MODULE 2

Earth Dams

Introduction, types of Earth dams, construction methods, Design criteria for Earth dams, causes of failure of earth dams, section of dam, preliminary design criteria, problems, control of seepage through earth dams, Safety measures.

Spillways

Introduction, essentials of a spillway, spillway components, factors affecting type & design of spillways. Ogee spillway (simple design problems). Energy dissipation below spillways (hydraulic jump- No design).

12 Hours

MODULE 3

Irrigation Design- Drawing

Design and Drawing with all the three views of:

1. Surplus weir with stepped apron
2. Tank sluice tower head
3. Canal gate sluice without tower head
4. Notch type Canal Drop

26 hours

Scheme of Examination;

- Compulsory question from module 3 for 20 marks.
- From module 1 and module 2, answer one full question from each module (2 x 15 = 30 marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Text book of irrigation engineering & Hydraulic Structures-R.K. Sharma, Oxford & IBH publishing Co., New Delhi (2002)
2. Irrigation & Water resources engineering- G.L. Asawa, New Age International Publishers, New Delhi (2005)
3. Irrigation, Water Resources & Water power engineering- Modi. P.N., Standard Book House, New Delhi
4. Design of minor irrigation and Canal structures- C. Sathya Narayana Murthy, Wiley eastern limited, New Delhi (1990)

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Irrigation engineering & Hydraulic structures- Garg.S.K.,khanna publishers, New Delhi
2. Hydraulic Structures & Irrigation Design Drawing -Dr.N. Balasubramanya, Tata Mcgraw-Hill Education Pvt.Ltd., New Delhi
3. Irrigation and Water Power Engineering- Madan Mohan Das &Mimi Das Saikia, PHI Learning Pvt.

VI Semester B.Tech

OPEN ELECTIVE 1

OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH & SAFETY IN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

Sub Code :	17SCV661	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	3	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours :	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. Students will be able to recognize and evaluate occupational safety and health hazards in the workplace
2. Determine appropriate hazard controls following the hierarchy of controls.
3. Able to analyze the effects of workplace exposures, injuries and illnesses, fatalities
4. Methods to prevent incidents using the hierarchy of controls,
5. Effective safety and health management systems and task oriented training.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Evaluate workplace to determine the existence of occupational safety and health hazards

CO2: Identify relevant regulatory and national consensus standards along with best practices that are applicable.

CO3: Select appropriate control methodologies based on the hierarchy of controls.

CO4: Analyze injury and illness data for trends.

CO5: Able to know the importance of different policies and labor act.

MODULE 1

Occupational Hazard and Control Principles: Safety, History and development, National Safety Policy. Occupational safety and Health Act (OSHA), Occupational Health and Safety administration - Laws governing OSHA and right to know. Accident – causation, investigation, investigation plan, Methods of acquiring accident facts, Supervisory role in accident investigation

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Ergonomics at Work Place: Ergonomics Task analysis, Preventing Ergonomic Hazards, Work space Envelops, Visual Ergonomics, Ergonomic Standards, Ergonomic Programs. Hazard cognition and Analysis, Human Error Analysis – Fault Tree Analysis – Emergency Response - Decision for action – purpose and considerations.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Fire Prevention and Protection: Fire Triangle, Fire Development and its severity, Effect of Enclosures, early detection of Fire, Classification of fire and Fire Extinguishers.

Electrical Safety, Product Safety: Technical Requirements of Product safety

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Health Considerations at Work Place: Types of diseases and their spread, Health Emergency. Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) – types and advantages, effects of exposure and treatment for engineering industries, municipal solid waste. Environment management plans (EMP) for safety and sustainability.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Occupational Health and Safety Considerations: Water and wastewater treatment plants, handling of chemical and safety measures in water and wastewater treatment plants and labs, Construction material manufacturing industries like cement plants, RMC Plants, precast plants and construction sites. Policies, roles and responsibilities of workers, managers and supervisors.

10 Hours

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

Text Books:

1. Goetsch D.L., (1999), “Occupational Safety and Health for Technologists, Engineers and Managers”, Prentice Hall.
2. Heinrich H.W., (2007), “Industrial Accident Prevention - A Scientific Approach”, McGraw-Hill Book Company National Safety Council and Associate (Data) Publishers Pvt. Ltd., (1991), “Industrial Safety and Pollution Control Handbook

Reference Books:

1. Colling D.A., (1990), “Industrial Safety Management and Technology”, Prentice Hall, New Delhi.
2. Della D.E., and Giustina, (1996), “Safety and Environmental Management”, Van Nostrand Reinhold International Thomson Publishing Inc.

VI Semester B.Tech
OPEN ELECTIVE 2
AIR POLLUTION & CONTROL

Sub Code : 17SCV662
Hrs/ Week : 3
Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To take up the basic concepts of air pollution.
2. To introduce students to basic concepts of pollution.
3. The contents involved the knowledge of causes of air pollution.
4. The contents involved the knowledge of health related to air pollution.
5. To develop skills relevant to control of air pollution.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Concepts of air pollution.

CO2: To estimate the quantity of air pollutant in the environment.

CO3: Be able to develop control technologies.

CO4: Able to understand the location of industrial plants to reduce pollution

CO5: Able to impart the knowledge of global warming and environmental policies

MODULE 1

Introduction: Definition, Sources, classification and characterization of air pollutants. Effects of air pollution on health, vegetation & materials. Types of inversion, photochemical smog.

08 hours

MODULE 2

Meteorology: Temperature lapse rate & stability, wind velocity & turbulence, plume behavior, measurement of meteorological variables, wind rose diagrams, Plume Rise, estimation of effective stack height and mixing depths. Development of air quality models-Gaussian dispersion model

12 hours

MODULE 3

Sampling: Sampling of particulate and gaseous pollutants (Stack, Ambient & indoor air pollution), Monitoring and analysis of air pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, SO_x, NO_x, CO, NH₃)

08 hours

MODULE 4

Control Techniques: Particulate matter and gaseous pollutants- settling chambers, cyclone separators, scrubbers, filters & ESP.

12 hours

MODULE 5

Air pollution due to automobiles, standards and control methods. Noise pollution causes, effects and control, noise standards. Environmental issues, global episodes, laws, acts, protocols

10 hours

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

Text Books:

1. M. N. Rao and H V N Rao, "Air pollution", Tata Mc-G raw Hill Publication.
2. H. C. Perkins, "Air pollution". Tata McGraw Hill Publication
3. Mackenzie Davis and David Cornwell, "Introduction to Environmental Engineering" McGraw-Hill Co.

Reference Books:

1. Noel De Nevers, "Air Pollution Control Engineering" , Waveland Pr Inc.
2. Anjaneyulu Y, "Text book of Air Pollution and Control Technologies", Allied Publisher

VI Semester B.Tech
OPEN ELECTIVE 3
TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT

Sub Code :	17SCV663	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	3	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours :	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To understand the concept of Quality
2. To understand the Implication of Quality on Business
3. To Implement Quality Implementation Programs
4. To have exposure to challenges in Quality Improvement Programs
5. To know the management and control of quality in any organization.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: To realize the importance of significance of quality
CO2: Manage quality improvement teams
CO3: Identify the requirements of quality improvement programs
CO4: Understand the basic concepts of TQM
CO5: Relate to public sector in quality system

MODULE 1

Introduction: Introduction - Need for quality, Evolution of quality, Definitions of quality, Dimensions of product and service quality, Basic concepts of TQM, TQM Framework, Contributions of Deming, Juran and Crosby, Barriers to TQM, Quality statements, Customer focus, Customer orientation, Customer satisfaction, Customer complaints and Customer retention, Costs of quality. **10 hours**

MODULE 2

TQM Principles: Leadership, Strategic quality planning, Quality Councils, Employee involvement, Motivation, Empowerment, Team and Teamwork, Quality circles Recognition and Reward, Performance appraisal, Continuous process improvement, PDCA cycle, 5S, Kaizen, Supplier partnership, Partnering, Supplier selection, Supplier Rating. **10 hours**

MODULE 3

TQM Tools & Techniques IT: The seven traditional tools of quality, New management tools, Six sigma: Concepts, Methodology, applications to manufacturing, service sector including IT, Bench marking, Reason to bench mark, Bench marking process, FMEA - Stages, Types. **10 hours**

MODULE 4

TQM Tools & Techniques: Control Charts, Process Capability, Concepts of Six Sigma, Quality Function Development (QFD), Taguchi quality loss function, TPM - Concepts, improvement needs, Performance measures. **10 hours**

MODULE 5

Quality Systems: Need for ISO 9000, ISO 9001 - 2008 Quality System - Elements, Documentation, Quality Auditing, QS 9000, ISO 14000 - Concepts, Requirements and Benefits, TQM - Implementation in manufacturing and service sectors. **10 hours**

Scheme of Examination:

Two question to be set from each module. Students have to answer five full questions, choosing at least one full question from each module.

Text Books:

1. OAKLAND, **J.S.** Total Quality Management – the route to improving performance Butterworth/Heinemann (1993)
2. HOYLE, D. ISO 9000 Quality Systems Handbook, 2nd Edition Butterworth/Heinemann 1997
3. TENNER, A.R. & De TORO I.J. Total Quality Management – Three Steps to Continuous Improvement (Addison –Wesley Publishing Company 1992)
4. BROWN, S. et al Strategic Operations Management, 2nd Edition Elsevier Butterworth-Heinemann 2005.

VI Semester B.Tech
GEOTECHNICAL ENGINEERING LABORATORY

Sub Code :	17SCVL67	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	2L+1T	Exam Hours :	3
Credits :	2	Exam Marks:	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To estimate index properties of soils (coarse and fine)
2. To estimate consistency limit of fine grained soils
3. To estimate shear strength of soils by direct shear test, triaxial shear test, vane shear test & unconfined compressive test
4. To estimate the engineering properties of the soils by density test, CBR test permeability test and consolidation test
5. To demonstrate miscellaneous equipment's such as Augers, Samplers, Rapid Moisture meter, Proctor's needle.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: To classify soil by physical observation of the soils

CO2: To classify soil based on estimated index and engineering characteristics of soils

CO3: To carry out interpolation among the estimated soil design parameters

CO4: Able to understand different strength test

CO5: Able to use miscellaneous equipment's

EXPERIMENTS

1. Identification of gravel type, sand type, silt type and clay types soils, Tests for determination of Specific gravity (for coarse and fine grained soils) and Water content (Oven drying method).
2. Grain size analysis of soil sample (sieve analysis).
3. In situ density by core cutter and sand replacement methods.
4. Consistency Limits – Liquid Limit (Casagrande and Cone Penetration Methods), plastic limit and shrinkage limit.
5. Standard Proctor Compaction Test and Modified Proctor Compaction Test.
6. Coefficient of permeability by constant head and variable head methods.
7. Strength Tests
 - a. Unconfined Compression Test
 - b. Direct Shear Test
 - c. Triaxial Compression Test (undrained)
8. Consolidation Test- Determination of compression index and coefficient of consolidation.

9. Laboratory vane shear test
10. Determination of CBR value
11. a) Demonstration of miscellaneous equipments such as Augers, Samplers, Rapid Moisture meter, Proctor's needle.
b) Demonstration of Hydrometer Test.
c) Demonstration of Free Swell Index and Swell Pressure Test
d) Demonstration of determination of relative density of sands.
12. Preparing a consolidated report of index properties and strength properties of soil

Scheme of Examination:

ONE question from major experiments: 20 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 20 marks

Viva – voce = 10 marks

Total: 50 marks

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engg.**-Punmia B.C.(2005), 16th Edition Laxmi Publications Co. , New Delhi.
2. **BIS Codes of Practice:** IS 2720(Part-3/Sec. 1) – 1987; IS2720 (Part – 2)- 1973; IS 2720 (Part – 4) – 1985; IS 2720(Part – 5) – 1985; IS 2720 (Part – 6) – 1972; IS 2720 (Part – 7) – 1980; IS 2720 (Part – 8) – 1983; IS 2720 (Part – 17) –1986; IS 2720 (Part - 10) – 1973; IS 2720 (Part – 13) – 1986;IS2720 (Part 11) – 1971; IS2720 (Part 15) – 1986; IS 2720(Part 30) – 1987; IS 2720 (Part 14) – 1977; IS 2720 (Part –14) – 1983; IS 2720 (Part – 28) – 1974; IS 2720 (Part – 29) –1966, IS 2720 (Part-60) 1965.
4. **Soil Testing for Engineers-** Lambe T.W., Wiley Eastern Ltd.,New Delhi.
5. **Manual of Soil Laboratory Testing-** Head K.H., (1986)- Vol. I, II, III, Princeton Press, London.

VI Semester B.Tech

CIVIL ENGINEERING EXTENSIVE SURVEY PROJECT WORK & VIVA VOCE

Sub Code : 17SCVL68

IA Marks : 50

Hrs/ Week : 2L+1T

Exam Hours : 3

Credits : 2

Exam Marks: 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To know thorough knowledge of the investigation and design of the projects
2. To know the procedure of submission of project report.
3. To impart the design and drawings in AUTO CAED
4. To know the importance of new tank projects
5. To impart the knowledge of water and sewage supply, highway and old tank projects

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to prepare contour map of the given area using different devices.

CO2: Understand field activity which provide real application of theoretical principles of surveying.

CO3: Able to doing simultaneously field work and office work.

CO4: Able to understand the importance of new tank project- estimate the requirement of water for future

CO5: Able to plan alternate routes, preparation of village maps and details of existing structures.

1. NEW TANK PROJECTS: The work shall consist of;

- a. Reconnaissance survey for selection of site and conceptualization of project.
- b. Alignment of center line of the proposed bund, Longitudinal and cross sections of the center line.
- c. Detailed survey required for project execution like Capacity surveys, Details at Waste weir and sluice points, Canal alignment etc. as per requirement
- d. Design and preparation of drawing with report. **10 Hours**

2. WATER SUPPLY AND SANITARY PROJECT: The work shall consist of;

- a. Reconnaissance survey for selection of site and conceptualization of project.
- b. Examination of sources of water supply, Calculation of quantity of water required based on existing and projected population.
- c. Preparation of village map by using total station.
- d. Survey work required for laying of water supply and UGD
- e. Location of sites for water tank. Selection of type of water tank to be provided. (Ground level, overhead and underground)
- f. Design of all elements and preparation of drawing with report. **10 Hours**

3. HIGHWAY PROJECT: The work shall consist of;

- a. Reconnaissance survey for selection of site and conceptualization of project.
- b. Preliminary and detailed investigations to align a new road (min. 1 to 1.5 km stretch) between two obligatory points. The investigations shall consist of topographic surveying of strip of land for considering alternate routes and for final alignment. Surveying by using total station.
- c. Report should justify the selected alignment with details of all geometric designs for traffic and design speed assumed.
- d. Drawing shall include key plan initial alignment, final alignment, longitudinal section along final alignment, typical cross sections of road. **10 Hours**

4. RESTORATION OF AN EXISTING TANK: The work shall consist of;

- a. Reconnaissance survey for selection of site and conceptualization of project.
- b. Alignment of center line of the existing bund, Longitudinal and cross sections of the center line.
- c. Detailed survey required for project execution like Capacity surveys, Details at Waste weir and sluice points, Canal alignment etc. as per requirement
- d. Design of all elements and preparation of drawing with report. **10 Hours**

5. TOWN/HOUSING / LAYOUT PLANNING: The work shall consist of;

- a. Reconnaissance survey for selection of site and conceptualization of project.
- b. Detailed survey required for project execution like contour surveys
- c. Preparation of layout plans as per regulations
- e. Centerline marking-transfer of centre lines from plan to ground
- f. Design of all elements and preparation of drawing with report as per regulations. **10 Hours**

Scheme of Examination;

- At the end of the semester students should submit the Extensive Survey Project Report
- Viva Voce

TEXT BOOKS:

1. 'Surveying' Vol 2 and Vol 3 - B. C. Punmia, Laxmi Publications
2. 'Plane Surveying' A. M. Chandra – New age international (P) Ltd
3. 'Higher Surveying' A.M. Chandra New age international (P) Ltd

VI Semester B.Tech
MINI PROJECT WORK

Sub Code : 17SCVP69

IA Marks : 50

Hrs/ Week: 3

Exam Marks: 50

Credits : 2

GUIDELINES:

Students should select a problem which addresses some basic home, office or other real life applications. Students have to collect an International Journal paper on the topics of their interest, prepare a write up and present with suitable demonstration by software or experimental work. Evaluation will be based on relevant topic students has studied, communication skill and reporting/documenting procedure or students may also advance software which is related to Civil Engineering for the project work.

Scheme of Examination;

- At the end of the semester students should submit the Mini Project Report
- Viva Voce

**VI Semester B.Tech
INTERNSHIP****Sub Code : 17SCV****Hrs/ Week: 3****Credits : 2****IA Marks : 50****Exam Marks: 50****Note: Internship / professional practice:**

This shall be carried out by students in industry setup related to the construction/materials testing laboratories/research organization/project management consulting firms/QS & QA organizations/planning and design offices/professional organization like ACCE/ICI/INSTRUCT/RMCMA/QCI, PMI,CIDC etc. & other avenues related to the domain in consultation and approval of internship guide/HOD/Internship committee of the institutions.

1. The professional certificate programs like ACCE(I)- SMP, ICI-BMTPC certifications, NSTRUCT-certifications, CIDC- certifications, RMC- QCI's RMCPCS certification programs, RMCMA-NRMCA'S concrete technologist India (CTI) programs and such similar programs by professional bodies with adequate industry exposures at sites/ RMC plant can be considered as internship/professional practice with due approvals from the guide/ HOD/ internship committees of the institutions.
2. The industry/organization should issue certificates of internship offer and its completion. The offer letter should clearly have the nature of work should be done by student and supervisor's name and duration of internship.
3. The student shall make a midterm and final presentation of the activities undertaken during the first six weeks and at the end of `12th week of internship respectively, to a panel comprising internship guide, a senior faculty from the department and head of the department. Each student should submit internship report at the end of semester with internship certificate.
4. Viva-voce examination shall be conducted by a panel of examiners consisting of internship supervisors from industry or industry professional approved by university and internship guide from the institute.
5. The college shall facilitate and monitor the internship program.
6. The internship should be completed during vacation after VI & VII semesters.

Scheme of Examination;

- At the end of the semester students should submit the Mini Project Report
- Viva Voce

VII Semester B.Tech
DESIGN OF STEEL STRUCTURES

Sub Code : 17SCV71	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 4	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 4	Exam Marks: 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To learn IS 800-2007 code of practice for the design of Compression, Tension and Flexural members using various cross-sections
2. To study the behavior and design of compression and tension members using simple and built-up sections
3. To understand behavior of flexural members and the design laterally restrained and unrestrained beams
4. To study the components of truss, loads on trusses, analysis and design of purlins and truss members
5. To study the design of bolted and welded connections.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to apply the IS code of practice for the design of steel structural elements

CO2: design compression and tension members using simple and built-up sections

CO3: Able to calculate forces on the various members of the truss and design them.

CO4: Able to analyze the behavior of bolted connections and design them

CO5: Able to design welded connections for both axial and eccentric forces.

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION: Advantages and Disadvantages of Steel structures, Loads and Load combinations, Design considerations, Limit State Method (LSM) of design, Failure criteria for steel, Codes, Specifications and section classification.

BOLTED CONNECTIONS: Introduction, Behavior of Bolted joints, Design strength of ordinary Black Bolts, Design strength of High Strength Friction Grip bolts (HSFG), Pin Connections, Simple Connections, Moment resistant connections, Beam to Beam connections, Beam and Column splices.

10Hours**MODULE 2**

WELDED CONNECTIONS: Introduction, Welding process, Welding electrodes, Advantages of Welding, Types and Properties of Welds, Types of joints, Weld symbols, Weld specifications, Design of welds, Simple joints, Moment resistant connections, Continuous Beam to Column connections, Continuous Beam to Beam connections, Beam Column splices.

10Hours**MODULE 3**

Design of Tension Members: Introduction, Types of tension members, Design of strands, Slenderness ratio, Behaviour of tension members, Modes of failure, Factors affecting the strength of tension members, Angles under tension, other sections, Design of tension member, Splices, Gussets.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Design of Compression Members: Introduction, Failure modes, Behaviour of compression members, Elastic buckling of slender compression members, Sections used for compression members, Effective length of compression members, Design of compression members, built up compression members.

Design of Column Bases: Design of simple slab base and gusseted base

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Plastic Behaviour of Structural Steel: Introduction, Plastic theory, Plastic hinge concept, Plastic collapse load, Theorem of Plastic collapse.

Design of Beams: Introduction, Beam types, , Lateral stability of beams, factors affecting lateral stability, Behaviour of simple and built-up beams in bending (without vertical stiffeners), Design strength of laterally supported beams in Bending, Design strength of laterally unsupported beams, Maximum deflection, Design of beam.

10 Hours

Note: Study of this course should be based on **IS: 800-2007**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(10 Mark x 05 Question = 50 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Design of Steel Structures, N. Subramanian, Oxford, 2008
2. Limit State Design of Steel Structures. Duggal. TATA Megra Hill 2010

REFERENCE:

1. Bureau of Indian Standards, IS800-2007, IS875-1987
2. Steel Tables

VII Semester B.Tech
QUANTITY SURVEYING AND VALUATION

Sub Code : 17SCV72	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 4	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 3	Exam Marks: 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To know the importance of preparing the types of estimates under different conditions
2. To know about the rate analysis and bill preparations
3. To study about the specification writing
4. To understand the valuation of land and buildings
5. To know the essentials of contract and its legal provisions.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Apply different types of estimates in different situations
 CO2: Carry out analysis of rates and bill preparation at different locations
 CO3: Demonstrate the concepts of specification writing
 CO4: Carry out valuation of assets
 CO5: Able to know the legal aspects on a breach of contract.

MODULE 1

ESTIMATION: Study of various drawings with estimates, important terms, units of measurement, abstract Methods of taking out quantities and cost –center line method, long and short wall method or crossing method. **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

Preparation of detailed and abstract estimates for the following Civil Engineering works – Buildings – RCC framed structures with flat, sloped RCC roofs with all Building components. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

ESTIMATE: Different type of estimates, approximate methods of estimating buildings, cost of materials. Estimation of wooden joineries such as doors, windows & ventilators.

ESTIMATES: Steel truss (Fink and Howe truss), manhole and septic tanks, RCC Culverts.

SPECIFICATIONS: Definition of specifications, objective of writing specifications, essentials in specifications, general and detail specifications of common item of works in buildings. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

RATE ANALYSIS: Definition and purpose. Working out quantities and rates for the following standard items of works – earth work in different types of soils, cement concrete of different mixes, bricks and stone masonry, flooring, plastering, RCC works, centering and form work for different RCC items, wood and steel works for doors, windows and ventilators.

MEASUREMENT OF EARTHWORK FOR ROADS: Methods for computation of earthwork – cross sections – mid section formula or average end area or mean sectional area, trapezoidal & prismoidal formula with and without cross slopes.

MODULE 5

CONTRACTS: Types of contract – essentials of contract agreement – legal aspects, penal provisions on breach of contract. Definition of the terms –Tender, earnest money deposit, security deposit, tender forms, documents and types. Acceptance of contract documents. Termination of contract, completion certificate, quality control, right of contractor, refund of deposit. Administrative approval – Technical sanction. Nominal muster roll, measurement books – procedure for recording and checking measurements –preparation of bills. Valuation- Definitions of various terms, method of valuation, Freehold & Leasehold properties, Sinking fund, depreciation and method of estimating depreciation, Outgoings.

10 Hours

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Estimating & Costing**, B. N. Dutta, Chand Publisher
2. **Quantity Surveying**- P.L. Basin S. Chand: New Delhi.
3. **Estimating & Specification** - S.C. Rangwala :: Charotar publishing house, Anand.

REFERENCE:

1. **Text book of Estimating & Costing**- G.S. Birde, Dhanpath Rai and sons: New Delhi.
2. **A text book on Estimating, Costing and Accounts**- D.D. Kohliand R.C. Kohli S. Chand: New Delhi.
3. **Contracts and Estimates**, B. S. Patil, University Press, 2006.

VII Semester B.Tech
ENVIRONMENTAL ENGINEERING – II

Sub Code : 17SCV731	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 4	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 3	Exam Marks: 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To learn the basics of sewage composition and its characteristics
2. To depict the information about various sewage treatment processes
3. To provide the adequate information on various disposal standards for industrial effluents
4. To study the information about air pollution and its effects
5. To understand the knowledge about solid waste generation and disposal methods

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Determine the sewage characteristics and design various sewage treatment plants
 CO2: Analyze the status of surface water and ground water quality and the remediation technologies
 CO3: Carry out municipal water and wastewater treatment system
 CO4: Design and operation manage hazardous wastes, risk assessment and treatment technologies
 CO5: Apply environmental treatment technologies and design processes

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION: Necessity for sanitation, methods of domestic wastewater disposal, types of sewerage systems and their suitability. Dry weather flow, factors affecting dry weather flow, flow variations and their effects on design of sewerage system; computation of design flow, estimation of storm flow, rational method and empirical formulae of design of storm water drain. Time of concentration.

DESIGN OF SEWERS: Hydraulic formulae for velocity, effects of flow variations on velocity, self-cleansing and non-scouring velocities, Design of hydraulic elements for circular sewers flowing full and flowing partially full (No derivations). **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

MATERIALS OF SEWERS: Sewer materials, shapes of sewers, laying of sewers, joints and testing of sewers, ventilation and cleaning of sewers.

SEWER APPURTENANCES: Catch basins, manholes, flushing tanks, oil and grease traps, Drainage traps. Basic principles of house drainage. Typical layout plan showing house drainage connections, maintenance of house drainage. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

WASTE WATER CHARACTERIZATION: Sampling, significance, techniques and frequency. Physical, Chemical and Biological characteristics, Aerobic and Anaerobic activity, CNS cycles. BOD and COD. Their significance & problems. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

DISPOSAL OF EFFLUENTS: Disposal of Effluents by dilution, self-purification phenomenon. Oxygen sag curve, Zones of purification, Sewage farming, sewage sickness, Effluent Disposal standards for land, surface water & ocean. Numerical Problems on Disposal of Effluents. Streeter Phelps equation.

TREATMENT OF WASTE WATER: Flow diagram of municipal wastewater treatment plant. Preliminary & Primary treatment: Screening, grit chambers, skimming tanks, primary sedimentation tanks – Design criteria & Design examples. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

SECONDARY TREATMENT: Suspended growth and fixed film bioprocess. Trickling filter – theory and operation, types and designs. Activated sludge process- Principle and flow diagram, Modifications of ASP, F/M ratio. Design of ASP.

Anaerobic Sludge digestion, Sludge digestion tanks, Design of Sludge drying beds. Low cost waste treatment method. Septic tank, Oxidation Pond and Oxidation ditches – Design. Reuse and recycle of waste water.

10 Hours

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Manual on Waste Water Treatment:** CPHEEO, Ministry of Urban Development, New Delhi.
2. **Water and Wastewater Engineering Vol-II:** - Fair, Geyer and Okun: John Willey Publishers, New York.
3. **Waste Water Treatment, Disposal and Reuse:** Metcalf and Eddyinc: Tata McGraw Hill Publications.

REFERENCE:

1. **Water Technology:** Hammer and Hammer
2. **Environmental Engineering:** Howard S. Peavy, Donald R. Rowe, George Tchobanoglous McGraw Hill International Edition.

VII Semester B.Tech
DESIGN OF PRE-STRESSED CONCRETE STRUCTURES

Sub Code : 17SCV732	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 4	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 3	Exam Marks: 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To learn the principles, materials, methods and systems of prestressing
2. To know the different types of losses and deflection of prestressed members
3. To learn the design of prestressed concrete beams for flexural, shear and tension and to calculate ultimate flexural strength of beam
4. To learn the design of anchorage zones, composite beams, analysis and design of continuous beam
5. To learn the design of water tanks.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1: Understanding of the behavior of prestressed concrete structures which is an advanced topic of civil engineering.
- CO2: Knowledge of calculation of effect of prestressing on statically determinate structures and statically indeterminate structures.
- CO3: Design, analysis, detailing and construction of prestressed concrete structural.
- CO4: Develop knowledge of contemporary issues
- CO5: Use the techniques, skill, and modern engineering tools necessary for pre-tensioning technology and post-tensioning technology.

MODULE 1

MATERIALS: High strength concrete and steel, Stress-Strain characteristics and properties.

BASIC PRINCIPLES OF PRESTRESSING: Fundamentals, Load balancing concept, Stress concept, center of Thrust. Pre-tensioning and post tensioning systems, tensioning methods and end anchorages.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

ANALYSIS OF SECTIONS FOR FLEXURE: Stresses in concrete due to pre-stress and loads, stresses in steel due to loads, Cable profiles.

LOSSES OF PRE-STRESS: Various losses encountered in pre-tensioning and post tensioning methods, determination of jacking force.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

DEFLECTIONS: Deflection of a pre-stressed member – Short term and long term deflections, Elastic deflections under transfer loads and due to different cable profiles. Deflection limits as per IS 1343. Effect of creep on deflection, load verses deflection curve, methods of reducing deflection

10 Hours

MODULE 4

LIMIT STATE OF COLLAPSE: Flexure -IS Code recommendations –Ultimate flexural strength of sections. Shear - IS Code recommendations, shear resistance of sections, shear reinforcement. Limit state of serviceability – control of deflections and cracking. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

DESIGN OF END BLOCKS: Transmission of prestress in pretensioned members, transmission length, Anchorage stress in post-tensioned members. Bearing stress and bursting tensile force-stresses in end blocks-Methods, I.S. Code, provision for the design of end block reinforcement.

DESIGN OF BEAMS: Design of pre-tensioned and post-tensioned symmetrical and asymmetrical sections. Permissible stress, design of prestressing force and eccentricity, limiting zone of pre-stressing force cable profile. **10 Hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Pre-stressed Concrete-** N. Krishna Raju - Tata Mc. Graw Publishers.
2. **Pre-stressed Concrete-** P. Dayarathnam: Oxford and IBH Publishing Co.

REFERENCES:

1. **Design of pre-stressed concrete structures-** T.Y. Lin and Ned H. Burns - John Wiley & Sons, New York.
2. **Fundamental of pre-stressed concrete-** N.C. Sinha & S.K. Roy
3. IS: 1343: 1980
4. **Pre-stressed Concrete-** N. Rajgopalan

**VII Semester B.Tech
MASONRY STRUCTURES**

Sub Code : 17SCV733
Hrs/ Week : 4
Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To introduce various fundamental concepts, components and types of masonry works.
2. To understand design features of brick masonry in buildings and laterally loaded masonry structures.
3. To understand basic concept and structural design of foundations, piers, walls and abutments.
4. To perform structural design of reinforced brick columns.
5. To analyze and design masonry arches and domes.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to understand fundamental concepts and the types of masonry works.

CO2: Able to design masonry structures

CO3: Able to know the strength of masonry structures and its effects

CO4: Able to design load bearing structures using codal provisions

CO5: Able to design earthquake resistant masonry structures.

MODULE 1

Introduction, Masonry units, materials and types: History of masonry Characteristics of Brick, stone, clay block, concrete block, stabilized mud block masonry units - strength, modulus of elasticity and water absorption. Masonry materials - Classification and properties of mortars, selection of mortars. **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

Strength of Masonry in Compression: Behaviour of Masonry under compression, strength and elastic properties, influence of masonry unit and mortar characteristics, effect of masonry unit height on compressive strength, influence of masonry bonding patterns on strength, prediction of strength of masonry in Indian context, Failure theories of masonry under compression. Effects of slenderness and eccentricity, effect of rate of absorption, effect of curing, effect of ageing, workmanship on compressive strength. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

Flexural and shear bond, flexural strength and shear strength: Bond between masonry unit and mortar, tests for determining flexural and shear bond strengths, factors affecting bond strength, effect of bond strength on compressive strength, orthotropic strength properties of masonry in flexure, shear strength of masonry, test procedures for evaluating flexural and shear strength. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

Design parameters of load bearing masonry buildings: Permissible compressive stress, stress reduction and shape reduction factors, increase in permissible stresses for eccentric vertical and lateral loads, permissible tensile and shear stresses, Effective height of walls and columns, opening in walls, effective

length, effective thickness, slenderness ratio, eccentricity, load dispersion, arching action, lintels; Wall carrying axial load, eccentric load with different eccentricity ratios, wall with openings, freestanding wall. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

Earthquake resistant masonry buildings: Behaviour of masonry during earthquakes, concepts and design procedure for earthquake resistant masonry, BIS codal provisions, Masonry arches, domes and vaults: Components and classification of masonry arches, domes and vaults, historical buildings, construction procedure. **10 Hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Hendry A.W., "Structural masonry"- Macmillan Education Ltd., 2nd edition
2. Sinha B.P & Davis S.R., "Design of Masonry structures"- E & FN Spon
3. Dayaratnam P, "Brick and Reinforced Brick Structures"- Oxford & IBH
4. Curtin, "Design of Reinforced and Prestressed Masonry"- Thomas Telford

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. Sven Sahlin, "Structural Masonry"-Prentice Hall
2. Jagadish K S, Venkatarama Reddy B V and Nanjunda Rao K S, "Alternative Building Materials and Technologies"- New Age International, New Delhi & Bangalore
3. IS 1905, BIS, New Delhi.
4. SP20(S&T), New Delhi.

VII Semester B.Tech
ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT

Sub Code :	17SCV741	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	4	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours :	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To ensure that Environmental considerations are addressed properly and incorporated into decision making process.
2. To avoid, minimize or balance the adverse significant bio-physical, social and other relevant effects of developmental projects.
3. To protect the productivity and capacity of natural system and ecological processes with maintain their function.
4. To promote development that is sustainable and optimize resources use and management opportunities.
5. Interpret options for evaluating environmental and social impacts

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: To encourage students to develop their own perspectives on impact assessment and to be able to relate this to other subject areas and to their wider understanding.

CO2: To identify and explore impact assessment fields and approaches.

CO3: To provide students with the knowledge and professional skills necessary to enable them to undertake environmental impact assessment.

CO4: To know importance of decision making

CO5: To know the importance of artificial infrastructure development

MODULE 1

Development Activity and Ecological Factors EIA, Rapid and Comprehensive EIA, EIS, FONSI. Need for EIA Studies, Baseline Information, Step-by-step procedures for conducting EIA, Limitations of EIA.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Frame work of Impact Assessment. Development Projects-Environmental Setting, Objectives and Scope, Contents of EIA, Methodologies, Techniques of EIA.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Assessment and Prediction of Impacts on Attributes Air, Water, Noise, Land Ecology, Soil, Cultural and Socio-economic Environment. EIA guidelines for Development Projects, Rapid and Comprehensive EIA. EIA guidelines for Development Projects, Rapid and Comprehensive EIA.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Public Participation in Environmental Decision making. Practical Considerations in preparing Environmental Impact Assessment and Statements. Salient Features of the Project Activity-Environmental Parameter Activity Relationships- Matrices. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

EIA for Water resource developmental projects, Highway projects: Nuclear-Power plant projects, Mining project (Coal, Iron ore), Thermal Power Plant, Infrastructure Construction Activities. **10 Hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Environmental Impact Analysis**-Jain R.K.-Van Nostrand Reinhold Co.
2. **Environment Impact Assessment**.-Anjaneyalu. Y.

REFERENCE:

1. Guidelines for EIA of developmental Projects Ministry of Environment and Forests, GOI.
2. **Environment Impact Assessment** - Larry W. Canter – Mc Graw Hill Publication.

VII Semester B.Tech
FINITE ELEMENT METHOD OF ANALYSIS

Sub Code : 17SCV742	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 4	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 3	Exam Marks: 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To study the strain –displacement and linear constitutive relation
- To understand the numerical techniques applied in FEM
- Establishment of element stiffness and load vector
- To study about the 2-D isoparametric concepts
- To analyze the 2-D frame elements using FEM techniques

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: demonstrate the differential equilibrium equations and their relationship

CO2: apply numerical methods to FEM

CO3: demonstrate the displacement models and load vectors

CO4: compute the stiffness matrix for isoperimetric elements

CO5: analyze plane stress and plane strain problems

MODULE 1

Basic concepts of elasticity - Kinematic and Static variables for various types of structural problems - approximate method of structural analysis- Finite difference method - Finite element method. Variation method and minimization of Energy approach of element formulation. Principles of finite element method - advantages & disadvantages - Finite element procedure. Finite elements used for one, two & three-dimensional problems - Element aspect ratio - mesh refinement vs. higher order elements - Numbering of nodes to minimize band width. **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

Nodal displacement parameters - Convergence criterion - Compatibility requirements - Geometric invariance - Shape function - Polynomial form of displacement function. Generalized and Natural coordinates **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

Isoparametric elements - Lagrangian interpolation function - shape functions for one, two & three-dimensional elements. Internal nodes and higher order elements - Sub parametric and Super parametric elements **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

Application of Finite Element Method for the analysis of one & two-dimensional problems - Analysis

of simple beams and plane trusses

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Application to Plates & Shells- Choice of displacement function (C^2 , C^1 and C^0 type) - Techniques for Non - linear Analysis.

10 Hours

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Krishnamoorthy C S, "Finite Element Analysis"- Tata McGraw Hill
2. Desai C and Abel J F, "Introduction to the Finite Element Method"- East West Press Pvt. Ltd., 1972
3. Bathe K J, "Finite Element Procedures in Engineering Analysis"- Prentice Hall

REFERENCE:

1. Rajasekaran. S, "Finite Element Analysis in Engineering Design"-Wheeler Publishing
2. Cook R D, Malkan D S & Plesta M.E, "Concepts and Application of Finite Element Analysis" - 3rd Edition, John Wiley and Sons Inc., 1989.
3. Shames I H and Dym C J, "Energy and Finite Element Methods in Structural Mechanics"- McGraw Hill, New York, 1985.

VII Semester B.Tech

HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT IN CONSTRUCTION

Sub Code : 17SCV743

Hrs/ Week : 4

Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50

Exam Hours : 2

Exam Marks: 50

Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To enable the students to understand the HR Management and system at various levels in general and in certain specific industries or organizations.
- To help the students focus on and analyze the issues and strategies required to select and develop manpower resources
- To develop relevant skills necessary for assessment and evaluation in construction industry
- To enable the students to understand the requirement of skills in construction industry
- To know the methods of training and development of personnel in construction industry

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: To have an understanding of the basic concepts, functions and processes of human resource management

CO2: To be aware of the role, functions and functioning of human resource department of the organizations.

CO3: To develop necessary skill set for application of various HR issues.

CO4: To analyze the strategic issues and strategies required to select and develop manpower resources.

CO5: To integrate the knowledge of HR concepts to take correct decisions.

MODULE 1

Introduction

Need of HRM in Construction Industry in context of globalization, Review the changing nature of construction employment, Elements of internal labor markets, Elements of external labor markets, Manpower types and planning, Different stages for manpower planning. **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

Nature and stages of a recruitment process

Nature and stages of a recruitment process within the construction environment, Elements of recruitment agencies, job centers and newspapers or specialist magazines for attracting potential recruit, Job description preparation, People specification preparation, Key elements of HRD such as basic literacy, functional skills, supervisory skills, entrepreneurship skills. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

Methods of training and development

Methods of training and development of personnel in the construction industry, Contemporary apprenticeship and skills certification scheme, Technical professional and management staff development options, Appraisal and review systems in construction organizations, Induction grievance and discipline procedures. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

Assessment and Evaluation

Training needs assessment, technical and managerial competencies necessary for achieving quality, preparation for training. Training for preparation of checklist necessary for RCC, Steel, Masonry works, and for commonly used work formats. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

Skills Required in Construction Industry

Need of Skills, Types of Skills, Different job roles in construction industry, Code and Regulations, National Skill Qualifications Framework (India) for Construction Industry, Professional Bodies in Construction Industry – RIBA, CIOB, RICS. **10 Hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Human Resource Management in Construction Projects, Martin Loosemore, Andrew Dainty, Helen Lingard, Taylor & Francis, 2003
2. Human Resource Management in Construction Projects: Strategic and Operational Approches, Martin Loosemore, Andrew Dainty and Helen Lingard.

REFERENCE:

1. Human Resource Management in Construction: Critical Perspectives, 2nd Edition, Andrew Dainty, Martin Loosemore.

VII Semester B.Tech
WATER RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

Sub Code :	17SCV751	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	4	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours :	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To build on the student's background in hydrology and hydraulics and understanding of water resources systems
- To develop the skills in modeling of flood flows and flood routing
- To develop skills in the ground water flow, type of aquifer and yield from the well
- To provide the knowledge of design of reservoir, operation and sedimentation
- To study the effect, causes and remedial measures of water logging

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Able to design various channel systems

CO2: Design head and cross regulator structures

CO3: To identify various types of reservoir and their design aspects

CO4: Will establish the understanding of cross drainage works and its design

CO5: Design different types of dams

MODULE 1

Surface and Ground water Resources

Hydrologic Cycle, Global water resources and Indian Water resources, Surface Water Resources, Water Balance, Available Renewable Water Resources, Water Scarcity, The Water Balance as a Result of Human Interference, Groundwater Resources, Types of Aquifers, Groundwater as a Storage Medium.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

Water Resources Planning and Management

Necessity, System components, planning scales, Approaches, planning and management aspects, Analysis, Models for impact prediction and evaluation, Adaptive Integrated Policies, Post Planning and management Issues.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

Integrated Water Resources Management:

Definition of IWRM, Principles, Implementation of IWRM, Legislative and Organizational Framework, Types and Forms of Private Sector Involvement.

10 Hours

MODULE 4

Water Governance and Water Policy

Legal Framework of Water, Substance of National Water Laws Other key issues, Changing incentives through Regulation, National Water Policy, National Level Commissions, Irrigation Management, Transfer Policies and Activities – Legal Registration of WUAs – Legal Changes in Water Allocation, Role of Local Institutions, Community Based Organizations, Water Policy Reforms: India.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Water Harvesting and Conservation

Water Harvesting Techniques – Micro-catchments, Design of Small Water Harvesting Structures – Farm Ponds – Percolation Tanks, Yield from a Catchment, Rain water Harvesting-various techniques related to rural and urban area.

10 Hours

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. K. Subramanya, “Engineering Hydrology”, Tata McGraw Hill Publishers, New Delhi.
2. H.M. Raghunath, “Ground Water”, Wiley Eastern Publication, New Delhi.
3. Daniel P. Loucks and Eelco van Beek, “Water Resources Systems. Planning and Management”, UNESCO Publication.

REFERENCE:

1. Mollinga, P. et al, “Integrated Water Resources Management”, Water in South Asia Volume I, Sage Publications, 2006.
2. Singh, Chhatrapati “Water Rights in India,” Ed: Chhatrapati Singh. Water Law in India: The Indian Law Institute, New Delhi, 1992.
3. Dhruva Narayana, G. Sastry, V. S. Patnaik, “Watershed Management”, CSWCTRI, Dehradun, ICAR Publications, 1997.

**VII Semester B.Tech
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY**

Sub Code : 17SCV752	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 4	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 3	Exam Marks: 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Understand some basic concepts of research and its methodologies
- Identify appropriate research topics
- Select and define appropriate research problem and parameters
- Prepare a project proposal (to undertake a project)
- Organize and conduct research (advanced project) in a more appropriate manner
- Write a research report and thesis

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Develop understanding on various kinds of research, objectives of doing research, research process, research designs and sampling.
- CO2:** Have basic knowledge on qualitative research techniques
- CO3:** Have adequate knowledge on measurement & scaling techniques as well as the quantitative data analysis
- CO4:** Have basic awareness of data analysis and hypothesis testing procedures
- CO5:** Compare and contrast quantitative and qualitative research paradigms, and explain the use of each in research

MODULE 1

Introduction

Introduction to Research Meaning of research, types of research, process of research, Sources of research problem, Criteria / Characteristics of a good research problem, Errors in selecting a research problem, Scope and objectives of research problem, formulation of research hypotheses, Search for causation, Developing a Research Proposal, Format of research proposal, Individual research proposal, Institutional research proposal, Significance, objectives, methodology, Funding for the proposal, Different funding agencies, Framework for the planning. **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

Literature Survey

Definition of literature and literature survey, Need of literature survey, Sources of literature, Elements and objectives of literature survey, Styles of literature survey, Strategies of literature survey. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

Data Collection, Measuring, Sampling and Scaling

Classification of data, benefits and drawbacks of data, Evaluation of data, Qualitative methods of data collection, Methods of qualitative research, Sampling, sample size, sampling strategy, attitude measurement and scaling, types of measurements, criteria of good measurements, classification of scales. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

Data Analysis Techniques

Testing of hypothesis - concepts and testing, Analysis of variance techniques, introduction to non-parametric tests, Validity and reliability, Approaches to qualitative and quantitative data analysis, Correlation and regression analysis, Introduction to factor analysis. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

Report Writing

Need of effective documentation, importance of report writing, types of reports, report structure, report formulation, Plagiarism, Research briefing, Presentation styles, Impact of presentation, Elements of effective presentation, Writing of research paper, Presenting and publishing paper, Patent procedure. **10 Hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Research Methodology: concepts and cases, Deepak Chawla and Neena Sondhi, Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.
2. Research Methods for Business, Sekaran Uma and Rogure Boudie, Wiley, India.
3. Research Methodology: Methods and Trends, by Dr. C. R. Kothari, New Age International Publishers.

REFERENCES:

1. Research Methods in Education, Louis Cohen, Manion, Morrison, Routledge (Taylor &Francis Group) / Cambridge University Press India Pvt. Ltd.
2. Research Methodology: An Introduction, Wayne Goddard and Stuart Melville.
3. Research Methodology: A Step by Step Guide for Beginners, by Ranjit Kumar.
4. Research in Education, John Best and James Kahn, Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd.

VII Semester B.Tech
PRINCIPLES OF TOWN PLANNING

Sub Code :	17SCV753	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	4	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours :	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

1. To understand the concept of balanced town by ensuring that new and existing facilities are complimentary to each other.
2. To provide sustainable buildings by considering the environmental, social and economic conditions.
3. To provide diversity of accommodation.
4. To provide leisure and cultural facilities for the town.
5. To create awareness about the traffic management within the town.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: To understand basic Principles of Planning

CO2: Analyze the data collected and apply suitable methods of planning

CO3: To learn Building Bye laws for residential and public building

CO4: Focus on the various recreational requirements of the town and preparation of master plan.

CO5: To learn fundamentals of town planning

MODULE 1

Introduction to building drawing: Definition, Need and importance of drawing in civil engineering, drawing sheets, graphical and numerical scale, lines, lettering and dimensioning. Building components, section of wall through door/window, sketches of building components, Conventional signs, symbols and abbreviations **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

Residential Building Drawing: Introduction to plan, elevation and section of the building, Development of detailed plan from line diagram, standard guidelines for building drawing

Planning of Residential Buildings: Principles of planning- architectural principle, Aspects of planning within and with respect to surroundings, Modular planning concept **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

Building Bye-Laws: Objectives, importance of bye-laws, F.S.I., Principles underlying building bye laws, rules governing light, parking, fire, water supply etc. Submission and Detailed drawings: Concept, key plan, site plan, structural drawing foundation plan, furniture arrangement, sanitary lines and traps, plumbing etc. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

Planning of public buildings: Buildings for different purposes like Education, Health, Recreation, Industry and Transportation, Spatial and land use planning, Elements of Perspective Drawing: Definition, concept and single and two-point perspective. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

Town Planning: Introduction, requirements, civil Survey, purpose, type, data required and presentation, Elements of city plan- Zoning, land use zoning and height zoning, growth of towns and Town planning scheme, Control of haphazard development. Industry: Priorities, classification, industrial estates, Redevelopment, Slum Improvement/clearance, master plan, town planning schemes, urban roads. Concept of green cities, green building. **10 Hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS

1. M. G. Shah, C. M. Kale and S. Y. Patki, Building Drawing with an integrated approach to Built Environment, Tata McGraw-Hill.
2. S. Kaleem A. Zaidi and Suhail Siddiqui, Drawing and Design of Residential and Commercial Buildings, Standard Publishers.

REFERENCES:

1. Y. N. RajaRao, Planning and Designing of residential building, Standard Publishers.
2. National building code of India.
3. Rangwala, S.C., Town planning, Charotar Publishing House.

VII Semester B.Tech
ENVIRONMENTAL ENGINEERING LABORATORY

Sub Code :	17SCVL76	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	2L+1T	Exam Hours :	3
Credits :	2	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours :	42

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To quantify the water and wastewater pollutant
- To measure the concentration of air pollutants
- To analyze the characteristics of water, wastewater and ambient air
- To study the growth of microorganism and its quantification
- To analyze optimum dosage of coagulant

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: quantify the pollutant concentration in water, wastewater and ambient air

CO2: recommend the degree of treatment required for the water and wastewater

CO3: analyze the survival conditions for the microorganism and its growth rate

CO4: Determine physical, chemical and biological characteristics of water and wastewater

CO5: Determine optimum dosage of coagulant

EXPERIMENTS

1. Determination of Solids in Sewage: Total Solids, Suspended Solids, Dissolved Solids, Volatile Solids, Fixed Solids, Settleable Solids.
2. Electrical conductivity. Determination of Chlorides and Sulphates.
3. Determination of Alkalinity, Acidity and pH.
4. Determination of Calcium, Magnesium and Total Hardness.
5. Determination of Dissolved Oxygen. Determination of BOD.
6. Determination of COD.
7. Determination of percentage of available chlorine in bleaching powder, Residual Chlorine and Chlorine Demand.
8. Jar Test for Optimum Dosage of Alum, Turbidity determination by Nephelometer.
9. Determination of Iron. Phenanthroline method.
10. Determination of Fluorides SPANDS Method.
11. MPN Determination
12. Determination Nitrates by spectrophotometer.
13. Determination of sodium and potassium by flame photometer.

Scheme of Examination:

ONE question from major experiments: 13 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 12 marks

Total: 25 marks

REFERENCES

1. **Manual of Water and Wastewater Analysis** – NEERI Publication.
2. **Standard Methods for Examination of Water and Waste water**(1995), American Publication – Association, Water Pollution Control Federation, American Water Works Association, Washington DC.
3. **IS Standards: 2490-1974, 3360-1974, 3307-1974.**
4. **Chemistry for Environment Engineering.** Sawyer and Mc Carthy,

VII Semester B.Tech
CONCRETE & HIGHWAY MATERIAL TESTING LABORATORY

Sub Code :	17SCVL77	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	2L+1T	Exam Hours :	3
Credits :	2	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours :	42

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To know the properties of concrete making materials
- To know the quality of fresh and hardened concrete
- To study the concrete mix design
- To know the properties of pavement materials
- To check the quality of pavement materials

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Conduct Quality Control tests on concrete making materials

CO2: Conduct Quality Control tests on fresh & hardened concrete

CO3: Design and test concrete mix

CO4: Characterize the pavement materials

CO5: Perform quality control tests on pavement materials

PART A

CEMENT: Normal Consistency, Setting time, Soundness by Autoclave method, Compression strength test and Air permeability test for fineness, Specific gravity of cement.

FRESH CONCRETE: Workability – slump, Compaction factor and Vee Bee tests.

HARDENED CONCRETE: Compression strength and Split tensile tests. Test on flexural strength of RCC beams, Permeability of concrete.

PART - B

SOIL: Density of Soil by Sand replacement method, CBR Text.

AGGREGATES: Crushing, abrasion, impact and Shape tests (Flaky, Elongation, Angularity number) Specific gravity and water absorption.

BITUMINOUS MATERIALS AND MIXES: Specific Gravity, Penetration, Ductility, Softening point, Flash and fire point, Viscosity, proportioning of aggregate mixes by Rothfutch Method, Marshall Stability tests.

Scheme of Examination:

ONE question from major experiments: 13 marks

ONE question from minor experiments: 12 marks

Total: 25 marks

REFERENCE BOOK:

1. Relevant IS Codes and IRC Codes.
2. **Highway Material Testing Laboratory Manual** by Khanna S Kand Justo, – CEG Nemi Chand & Bros.
3. M. L. Gambhir: Concrete Manual: Dhanpat Rai & sons New –Delhi.

**VII Semester B.Tech
MAJOR PROJECT PHASE – 1**

Sub Code : 17SCVL78

Hrs/ Week: 3

Credits : 2

IA Marks : 100

Exam Hours : 2

Total Marks : 100

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To support independent learning.
- To develop interactive, communication, organization, time management, and presentation skills.
- To impart flexibility and adaptability.
- To inspire independent and team working.
- To expand intellectual capacity, credibility, judgment, intuition.
- To adhere to punctuality, setting and meeting deadlines.
- To instill responsibilities to oneself and others.
- To train students to present the topic of project work in a seminar without any fear, face audience confidently, enhance communication skill, involve in group discussion to present and exchange ideas.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Describe the project and be able to defend it.

CO2: Develop critical thinking and problem solving skills.

CO3: Learn to use modern tools and techniques.

CO4: Communicate effectively and to present ideas clearly and coherently both in written and oral forms.

CO5: Develop skills to work in a team to achieve common goal.

CO6: Develop skills of project management and finance.

CO7: Develop skills of self-learning, evaluate their learning and take appropriate actions to improve it.

CO8: Prepare them for life-long learning to face the challenges and support the technological changes to meet the societal needs.

Project Work Phase - I:

Each student of the project batch shall involve in carrying out the project work jointly in constant consultation with internal guide, co-guide, and external guide and prepare the project report as per the norms avoiding plagiarism.

Evaluation Procedure:

- As per University guidelines
- Internal Marks: The Internal marks (100 marks) evaluation shall be based on Phase wise completion of the project work, Project report, Presentation and Demonstration of the actual/model/prototype of the project.

VIII Semester B.Tech
DESIGN AND DRAWING OF STEEL STRUCTURES

Sub Code : 17SCV81	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 4	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 4	Exam Marks: 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Analysis and design of steel members and connections.
- Understand the concept of buckling, shear, bending of members subjected to combined forces
- Understand the design of structural steel components (members and connections in two - dimensional (2D) truss and frame structures).
- Ability to perform analysis and design of steel members and connections and design steel structural systems as per the latest IS code.
- Assess the effective use of the latest industry standard formulas, tables, design aids in the design of steel members.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Identify the loads and loads combination acting on the members.

CO2: Understand the design philosophy of steel structures and the importance of limit state design method.

CO3: Design simple bolted and welded connections for tension and compression members and beams.

CO4: Analyze and design of tension members, compression members and beams

CO5: Identify the different failure modes of bolted and welded connections and determine their design strengths

MODULE 1

(Drawings to be prepared for given structural details)

CONNECTIONS: Bolted and welded, beam-beam, Beam-column, seated, stiffened and un-stiffened.

COLUMNS: Splices, Column-column of same and different sections. Lacing and battens.

COLUMN BASES: Slab base and Gusseted base.

08 (T) + 12 (D)

MODULE 2

Design and drawing of following

i) Roof Truss (Bolted connection, Forces in the members to be given)

ii) Gantry Girder

iii) Plate Girder (Welded)

10 (T) + 20 (D)

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: Choosing at least **ONE** full question from module 1.

(15 Mark x 1 Question = 15 Marks)

PART B: Choosing at least **ONE** full question from module 2.

(35 Mark x 1 Question = 35 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Structural Design & Drawing** – N. Krishna Raju, Universities Press, India.
2. **Design of Steel Structures** - N. Subramanian: Oxford University ,Press.
3. **Design of Steel Structures** - Negi - Tata Mc Graw Hill Publishers.

REFERENCE:

4. **Design of Steel Structures** - Arya and Ajaman- Nem Chand &Bros. Roorkee.
5. **Design of Steel Structures** - Raghupati
6. IS: 800 – 2007,
7. SP 6 (1) – 1984 or Steel Table.

**VIII Semester B.Tech
PAVEMENT DESIGN**

Sub Code : 17SCV821
Hrs/ Week : 3
Credits : 3

IA Marks : 50
Exam Hours : 2
Exam Marks: 50
Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To study about the types and components of pavements
- To learn about the stresses in flexible pavements and equivalent single wheel load
- To study the design of flexible pavements
- To learn about the stresses in rigid pavements
- To study the design of rigid pavements

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Identify the pavement components and compare highway and airport pavements

CO2: Calculate stresses and ESWL in flexible pavements

CO3: Design the flexible pavement using empirical and semi empirical methods

CO4: Analyze the warping, friction, wheel load stress and calculate the combined stress

CO5: Design rigid pavements by IRC method and evaluate the pavements

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION: Desirable characteristics of pavement, type's and components, Difference between Highway pavement and Air field pavement– Design strategies of variables – Functions of sub-grade, sub base – Base course – surface course – comparison between Rigid and flexible pavement.

FUNDAMENTALS OF DESIGN OF PAVEMENTS: Design life – Traffic factors – climatic factors – Road geometry – Subgrade strength and drainage, Stresses and deflections, Boussinesqs theory – principle, Assumptions –Limitations and problems on above - Busmister theory – Two layered analysis – Assumptions – problems on above

12 Hours

MODULE 2

DESIGN FACTORS: Design wheel load – contact pressure – ESWL concept – Determination of ESWL by equivalent deflection criteria – Stress criteria – EWL concept.

FLEXIBLE PAVEMENT DESIGN: McLeod Method –Kansas method – Tri-axial method - CBR method – IRC Method (old) -CSA Method using IRC 37-2001.

12 Hours

MODULE 3

STRESSES IN RIGID PAVEMENT: Principle – Factors - wheel load and its repetition – properties of sub grade External conditions – joints – Reinforcement – Analysis of stresses – Assumptions –

Westergaard's Analysis – Modified Westergaard equations –Critical stresses – Wheel load stresses, Warping stress – Frictional stress –combined stresses (using chart / equations) - problems on above.

6 Hours

MODULE 4

DESIGN OF RIGID PAVEMENT: Design of C.C. Pavement by IRC: 38 –2002 for dual and Tandem axle load – Reinforcement in slabs –Requirements of joints – Types of joints – Expansion joint – contraction joint– warping joint – construction joint – longitudinal joint, Design of joints, Design of Dowel bars, Design of Tie bars – problems on above.

08 Hours

MODULE 5

FLEXIBLE PAVEMENT FAILURES, MAINTENANCE ANDEVALUATION: Types of failures, causes, remedial/maintenance measures in flexible pavements – Functional Evaluation by visual inspection and unevenness measurement by using different techniques - Structural Evaluation by Benkelman Beam Deflection Method, Falling weight deflectometer, GPR Method.

RIGID PAVEMENT FAILURES, MAINTENANCE ANDEVALUATION: Types of failures, causes, remedial/maintenance measures in rigid pavements – Functional Evaluation by visual inspection and unevenness measurements.

Design factors for Runway Pavements – Design methods for Airfield pavements.

12 Hours

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Highway Engineering-** Khanna & Justo
2. **Principles & Practices of Highway Engineering-** L R Kadiyalli & N B. Lal
3. **Pavement Analysis & Design** - Yang H. Huang- II edition.
4. Relavent IRC codes

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Principles of Pavement Design-** Yoder and Witzack - 2nd edition, John Wileys and Sons
2. **Principles of Pavement Design-** Subha Rao

**VIII Semester B.Tech
HIGHWAY GEOMETRIC DESIGN**

Sub Code : 17SCV822	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 3	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 3	Exam Marks: 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Develop an understanding of the principles of geometric design in the context of transportation planning and traffic design.
- To focus on climatic and environmental factors, aesthetics and adaptation to surroundings.
- Apply basic science principles in estimating stopping and passing sight distance requirements
- Understand the design criteria for geometric design of highways.
- Design basic horizontal and vertical alignment of the highway

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Learn concepts and characteristic for proper design.

CO2: Apply standards, guidelines, and practiced knowledge to perform designs.

CO3: Assess the environmental impacts of location and design of roads

CO4: Prepare detailed plans for such infrastructure elements.

CO5: Understand the road building process within the context of laws and regulations

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION: Geometric Control factors like Topography – design speed – design vehicle – Traffic – Capacity – volume – environment and other factors as per IRC and AASHTO standards and specifications - PCU concept – factors controlling PCU for different design purpose.

CROSS SECTIONAL ELEMENTS: Pavement surface characteristics – friction – skid resistance – pavement unevenness - light reflecting characteristics – camber – objectives – types of camber – methods of providing cambers in the field – problems – carriage way – kerb – median – shoulder – foot path – parking lanes – service roads – cycle tracks – Driveways – Right of way – Factors influencing right of way – Design of Road humps as per latest IRC provisions. **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

SIGHT DISTANCE: Importance, types, Side distance at uncontrolled intersection, derivation, factors affecting side distance, IRC, AASHTO standards, problems on above. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

HORIZONTAL ALIGNMENT: Definition, Checking the stability of vehicle, while moving on horizontal curve, Super elevation, Ruling minimum and maximum radius, Assumptions – problems –

method of providing super elevation for different curves – Extra widening of pavement on curves – objectives – Mechanical widening – psychological widening – Transition curve – objectives – Ideal requirements – Types of transition curve – Method of evaluating length of transition curve – Setting the transition curve in the field, set back distance on horizontal curve. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

VERTICAL ALIGNMENT: Gradient – Types of gradient – Design criteria of summit and valley curve – Design of vertical curves based on SSD – OSD– Night visibility considerations – Design standards for hilly roads –problems on the above.

INTERSECTION DESIGN: Principle – At grade and Grade separated junctions – Types – channelization – Features of channelizing Island –median opening – Gap in median at junction. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

ROTARY INTERSECTION: Elements – Advantages – Disadvantages – Design guide lines – problem on the above – Grade separated intersection –Three legged inter section – Diamond inter change – Half clover leaf – cloverleaf- Advantages- Disadvantages only.

HIGHWAY DRAINAGE: Importance – sub surface drainage –surface drainage – Design of road side drives – Hydrological – Hydraulically considerations and design of filter media, problems on above. **10 Hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: **TEN** multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: **TWO** question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Principle and practice of Highway Engineering-** L R KADIYALI& N B LAL: Khanna publications
2. **Highway Engineering** – Khanna S K & Justo, Nemchand & Bros.
3. **Highway Engineering** by Srinivas Kumar.

REFERENCE BOOKS:

1. **Highway Engineering-** Kadiyali L R : Khanna publications
2. **Relavent IRC** Publications
3. **Transportation Engineering and Planning-** Papa Coostasand Prevendors PHI, New Delhi.

**VIII Semester B.Tech
ADVANCED CONCRETE TECHNOLOGY**

Sub Code : 17SCV823	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 3	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 3	Exam Marks: 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To understand on cement chemistry and influence of other cementitious materials to the progress of hydration reaction
- To know chemical and physical interaction of aggregates and admixtures with the hydrated cement paste and their effects on the performance of fresh and hardened concrete.
- To know concrete durability problems
- Expected physical and chemical changes occurring on the concrete microstructure during the progress of durability problems and precautions to be taken.
- Manufacture of special concretes and their properties.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Discuss the concrete ingredients and its influence at gaining strength.

CO2: Design of concrete mix and grade as per IS codes.

CO3: Summarize the concepts of conventional concrete and its differences with other concretes like no fines, light weight etc.

CO4: Describe the application and use of fiber reinforced concrete.

CO5: Design and develop the self-compacting and high performance concrete.

MODULE 1

Importance of Bogue's compounds, Structure of a Hydrated Cement Paste, Volume of hydrated product, porosity of paste and concrete, transition Zone, Elastic Modulus, factors affecting strength and elasticity of concrete, Rheology of concrete in terms of Bingham's parameter.

CHEMICAL ADMIXTURES- Mechanism of chemical admixture, Plasticizers and super Plasticizers and their effect on concrete property in fresh and hardened state, retarder, accelerator, Air-entraining admixtures, new generation superplasticiser.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

MINERAL ADMIXTURE- Fly ash, Silica fume, GCBS, and their effect on concrete property in fresh state and hardened state.

MIX DESIGN - Factors affecting mix design, design of concrete mix by BIS method using IS10262 and current American (ACI)/ British (BS) methods. Provisions in revised IS10262-2004.

12 Hours

MODULE 3

DURABILITY OF CONCRETE - Introduction, Permeability of concrete, chemical attack, acid attack, efflorescence, Corrosion in concrete. Thermal conductivity, thermal diffusivity, specific heat. Alkali Aggregate Reaction, IS456-2000 requirement for durability.

08 Hours

MODULE 4

RMC concrete - manufacture, transporting, placing, precautions, Methods of concreting- Pumping, under water concreting, shotcrete, High volume fly ash concrete, Self-compacting concrete concept and tests
Fiber reinforced concrete - Fibers types and properties, Ferro cement - materials, techniques of manufacture, properties and application

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Light weight concrete-materials properties and types. Typical light weight concrete mix High density concrete and high performance concrete-materials, properties and applications.
Test on Hardened concrete- Compression, tension and flexure tests. NDT tests concepts-Rebound hammer, pulse velocity methods.

10 Hours

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. **Properties of Concrete**- Neville, A.M. - ELBS Edition, Longman Ltd., London
2. **Concrete Technology**- M.S. Shetty
3. **Concrete Technology**- A.R. Santhakumar,-Oxford University Press.
4. **Concrete**- P.K. Mehta, P J M Monteiro, - Prentice Hall, New Jersey (Special Student Edition by Indian Concrete Institute Chennai)

REFERENCE:

1. ACI Code for Mix Design and IS 10262-2004.
2. **Concrete Mix Design**- N. Krishna Raju - Sehgal Publishers
3. **Concrete Manual**- Gambhir M.L.- Dhanpat Rai & Sons, New Delhi
4. **Advanced Concrete Technology Processes**- John Newman, BanSeng Choo, - London.
5. **Advanced Concrete Technology Constituent materials**- John Newman, Ban Seng Choo- London
6. **Non-Destructive Test and Evaluation of Materials**- J. Prasad, C GK Nair,-Mc Graw Hill.

VIII Semester B.Tech
QUALITY ASSURANCE IN CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS

Sub Code :	17SCV831	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	3	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours :	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To understand the fundamentals of quality management for a project-based industry.
- To know the theories, principles and processes in quality management.
- To know the differences between quality control and quality management.
- To apply quality management best practice in construction in terms of both processes and attitudes.
- To encounter problems in construction and describe how to assure quality adherence

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Understand the fundamentals of quality management for a project-based industry.

CO2: Demonstrate knowledge of the theories, principles and processes in quality management.

CO3: Recognize the differences between quality control and quality management.

CO4: Apply quality management best practice in construction in terms of both processes and attitudes.

CO5: Design and evaluate solutions to problems encountered in construction and describe how to assure quality adherence.

MODULE 1

INTRODUCTION TO QUALITY MANAGEMENT

Foundations of Total Quality Management: Understanding quality, TQM philosophy: Concept of Deming, Juran, Crosby, Imai, Ishikawa, Taguchi, Shingo philosophies. Models and frame works.

10 Hours

MODULE 2

QUALITY MANAGEMENT TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES

TQM Tools: An overview of Flowcharts, Check sheets, Histogram, Cause and effect diagrams, Pareto diagram, Scatter diagram and Control charts.

Planning: Policy, Strategy and goal deployment, Partnership and resources, Design for quality.

10 Hours

MODULE 3

QUALITY ASSURANCE AND CONTROL

Objectives – Regularity agent, owner, design, contract and construction-oriented objectives, methods – Techniques and needs of QA/QC – Different aspects of quality – Appraisals, Factors influencing construction quality – Critical, major failure aspects and failure mode analysis, – Stability methods and tools, optimum design – Reliability testing, reliability coefficient and reliability prediction.

10 Hours**MODULE 4****TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT**

Implementing TQM: TQM and management of change, Planning and implementation of TQM, Sustained improvement, TQM models in practice. ISO 9000 quality systems, six sigma practice. Customer-Supplier Chain, Continuous improvement. ISO 14001 quality systems.

10 Hours**MODULE 5****QUALITY IMPROVEMENT TECHNIQUES**

Selection of new materials – Influence of drawings, detailing, specification, standardization – Bid preparation – Construction activity, environmental safety, social and environmental factors – Natural causes and speed of construction – Life cycle costing – Value engineering and value analysis.

10 Hours**SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:**

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)**TEXT BOOKS:**

1. Hutchins.G, ISO 9000: A Comprehensive Guide to Registration, Audit Guidelines and Successful Certification, Viva Books Pvt. Ltd., 1994.
2. James, J.O' Brian, Construction Inspection Handbook – Total Quality Management, Van Nostrand, 1997

REFERENCE:

1. John L. Ashford, The Management of Quality in Construction, E & F.N.Spon, 1989.
2. Juran Frank, J.M. and Gryna, F.M. Quality Planning and Analysis, McGraw Hill, 2001
3. Kwaku.A., Tena, Jose, M. Guevara, Fundamentals of Construction Management and Organisation, Reston Publishing Co., Inc., 1985.

**VIII Semester B.Tech
BUILDING SERVICES**

Sub Code : 17SCV832	IA Marks : 50
Hrs/ Week : 3	Exam Hours : 2
Credits : 3	Exam Marks : 50
	Total Hours : 50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To understand the types of MEP systems and its suitability in construction industry
- To plan various types of mechanical services and HVAC as per the requirements of buildings
- To apply various types of electrical and fire fighting services as per the requirements of building and Govt Regulations
- To provide Plumbing, Sound and Thermal insulation as per the needs of client
- To know the importance and requirement of rain water harvesting, Solid Waste Management.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Demonstrate an understanding of the need for different types of MEP systems and select suitable type
- CO2:** Recognize the implications of building design for mechanical, electrical and plumbing (MEP) service provision including appreciation of the design and construction for high efficiency and sustainable building services
- CO3:** Illustrate services installation including fire safety and ventilation
- CO4:** Manage the hand-over and commissioning processes for services
- CO5:** Plan for Rain Water Harvesting and Solid Waste Management in the new buildings.

MODULE 1

Water Supply, Drainage and Solid Waste Disposal

Water requirements for different types of buildings, simple method of removal of impurities, water saving practices and their potential, Service connection from mains, sump and storage tank, Types and sizes of pipes used in multistoried buildings.

Types of fixtures and fitting for a contemporary bathroom – taps – quarter turn, half turn, ceramic, foam flow etc, hot water mixer, hand shower. Rainwater harvesting, sizes of rainwater pipes and typical detail of a water harvesting pit. Principles of drainage, surface drainage, shape and sizes of drains and sewers, storm water over flow chambers. Approaches for solid waste management, Solid wastes collection, On-site processing and disposal methods.

12 Hours

MODULE 2

Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC)

Behaviour of heat propagation, thermal insulating materials and their co-efficient of thermal conductivity. General methods of thermal insulation: Thermal insulation of roofs, exposed walls. Ventilation:

Definition and necessity, system of ventilation. Principles of air conditioning, Air cooling, Different systems of ducting and distribution, Essentials of air-conditioning system. **08 Hours**

MODULE 3

Electrical Services

Electrical systems, Single/Three phase supply, Protective devices in electrical installation, Earthing and Grounding, ISI Specifications. Electrical installations in buildings - Types of wires, Wiring systems and their choice, Planning electrical wiring for building, Main and Distribution boards, Preparation of Electrical Layout for a house or building. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

Fire Fighting Services

Classification of buildings based on occupancy, causes of fire and spread of fire, Standard fire, Firefighting, protection and fire resistance, Firefighting equipment and different methods of fighting fire, means of escape, alarms, etc., Combustibility of materials, Structural elements and fire resistance, Fire escape routes, Wet risers, dry risers, sprinklers, heat detector, smoke detectors, fire dampers, fire doors, etc., Provisions of NBC, Preparation of Plumbing and Fire Fighting layout for a residential or public building. **10 Hours**

MODULE 5

Engineering Services

Engineering services in a building as a system, Lifts, escalators, cold and hot water systems. Pumps and Machineries: Reciprocating, Centrifugal, Deep well, Submersible, Automatic pumps, Sewerage pumps, Compressors, Vacuum pumps, Hot water boilers – Classification and types of lifts, Escalators - their uses, types and sizes, safety norms to be adopted – Social features required for physically handicapped and elderly, Generators.

Building Maintenance: Preventive and protective maintenance, Planning of Scheduled and contingency maintenance, Maintenance standards. Economic maintenance decisions. **10 Hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Charangith Shah, Water supply and sanitary engineering, Galgotia publishers.
2. Kamala & DL Kanth Rao, Environmental Engineering, Tata McGraw Hill publishing co. Ltd.
3. Technical teachers Training Institute (Madras), Environmental Engineering, Tata McGraw Hill publishing Co. Ltd.
4. M. David Egan, Concepts in Building Fire Safety.

REFERENCE:

1. O.H.Koenigsberger, "Manual of Tropical Housing and Building", Longman Group United Kingdom
2. V.K.Jain, Fire Safety In Building 2edition, New Age International Publishers
3. E.G.Butcher, Smoke control in Fire-safety Design.
4. E.R.Ambrose, Heat pumps and Electric Heating, John and Wiley and Sons Inc, New York
5. Handbook for Building Engineers in Metric systems, NBC, New Delhi.
6. National Building Code , HSE Regulations.

VIII Semester B.Tech
SUSTAINABILITY AND GREEN CONSTRUCTION

Sub Code :	17SCV833	IA Marks :	50
Hrs/ Week :	3	Exam Hours :	2
Credits :	3	Exam Marks:	50
		Total Hours :	50

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To expose the students to the concepts of sustainability in the context of building and conventional engineered building materials
- To use and compare relevant codes
- Exposing the student to concepts of embodied, operational and life cycle energy, minimizing energy consumption by optimal design
- Learn the principles of planning orientation of buildings and reuse of building materials
- Acquire knowledge on various aspects of green construction

COURSE OUTCOMES:

CO1: Identify and compare existing energy codes, green building codes and green rating Systems.

CO2: Identify and use construction materials and methods that more easily allow for salvage and re-use of building materials.

CO3: Perform demolition in ways that allow for salvage of re-usable building materials.

CO4: Understand the techniques and benefits of building performance testing, monitoring and metering.

CO5: Identify and make use of techniques for weatherization and sustainable remodeling of existing structures.

MODULE 1

Introduction

Introduction to Green Building, Principles of Green Building – Site aspect, Soil conservation, Vegetation retention, Energy efficiency, Materials and Resources, Water efficiency, Rainwater Harvesting, Grey water gardening, Solid waste management, Solar energy system. **10 Hours**

MODULE 2

Green Materials

Necessity and importance of sustainable construction materials, Material composition and properties, Production, Storage, Distribution, Testing, Acceptance criteria, Limitations of use, Economic consideration, and recent developments related to the following materials to be studied. **10 Hours**

MODULE 3

Admixtures in Concrete

Various construction chemicals / admixtures, Fly ash and its use in concrete, GGBS and its use in concrete, Silica fume concrete, Self-compacting concrete, Fiber reinforced plastics and concrete, Light weight concrete, Light weight cement blocks. **10 Hours**

MODULE 4

Special Concrete

High performance concrete, Nano Technology in cement concrete, Ferro cement Technology, Crumb modified bitumen rubber, Glenium concrete, Materials used in nuclear containment structures.

10 Hours

MODULE 5

Green Standards

Energy Conservation Building Codes, Indian Green Building Council, Application, Compliance Mechanism, Procedure for erection of Code compliant building, Renewable Energy, Responsibilities and duties - Owners, Empanelled Energy Auditors (Building), State designated agency. **10 Hours**

SCHEME OF EXAMINATION FOR END SEMESTER EXAMINATION OF 50 MARKS:

PART A: TEN multiple Choice Questions to be set for **ONE MARK** each.

(01 Mark x 10 Question = 10 Marks)

PART B: TWO question to be set from each module. Students have to answer **FIVE** full questions, Choosing at least **ONE** full question from each module.

(08 Mark x 05 Question = 40 Marks)

TEXT BOOKS:

1. Concrete Technology by Neville
2. Construction Materials, Methods & Techniques (3e) by William P Spence, Yesdee Publication 2012, Pvt. Ltd, Chennai, India
3. Concrete Structure properties & Materials by Mehta P.K & Mantreio P.J.M, Prentice Hall.
4. Concrete Technology by M.S.Shetty, S.Chand Publications

REFERENCES:

1. Building Materials by M L Gambhir, Neha Jamwal, Tata McGraw Hill Publ.
2. New Building Materials and Construction World magazine
3. Ferrocement Construction Manual by Dr. D.B.Divekar, 1030, Shivaji Nagar, Model Colony, Pune
4. Civil Engineering and Construction Review magazine
5. Engineering Materials by Dr. S.V.Deodhar

**VIII Semester B.Tech
TECHNICAL SEMINAR**

Sub Code : 17SCV84
Hrs/ Week : 3
Credits : 2

IA Marks : 100
Exam Hours: 2
Total Marks: 100

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- Conduct literature survey in the domain area to find appropriate topic.
- Prepare the synopsis report with own sentences in a standard format.
- Learn to use MS word, MS power point, MS equation and Drawing tools or any such facilities in the preparation of report and presentation.
- Present the seminar topic orally and/or through power point slides.
- Communicate effectively to answer the queries and involve in debate/discussion.
- The participants shall take part in discussion to foster friendly and stimulating environment in which the students are motivated to reach high standards and become self-confident.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Develop knowledge in the field of Civil Engineering and other disciplines through independent learning and collaborative study.
- CO2:** Identify and discuss the current, real-time issues and challenges in engineering & technology.
- CO3:** Develop written and oral communication skills.
- CO4:** Explore concepts in larger diverse social and academic contexts.
- CO5:** Apply principles of ethics and respect in interaction with others.
- CO6:** Develop the skills to enable life-long learning.

Evaluation Procedure:

- As per University guidelines.
- The Internal Assessment marks for the seminar shall be awarded based on the relevance of the seminar topic, quality of the report, presentation skills, participation in the question and answer, and attendance in the seminar classes/sessions.

**VIII Semester B.Tech
MAJOR PROJECT PHASE – 2**

Sub Code : 17SCV85
Hrs/ Week : 6
Credits : 8

IA Marks : 100
Exam Hours: 2
Exam Marks: 100

COURSE OBJECTIVES:

- To support independent learning.
- To develop interactive, communication, organization, time management, and presentation skills.
- To impart flexibility and adaptability.
- To inspire independent and team working.
- To expand intellectual capacity, credibility, judgment, intuition.
- To adhere to punctuality, setting and meeting deadlines.
- To instill responsibilities to oneself and others.
- To train students to present the topic of project work in a seminar without any fear, face audience confidently, enhance communication skill, involve in group discussion to present and exchange ideas.

COURSE OUTCOMES:

- CO1:** Describe the project and be able to defend it.
- CO2:** Develop critical thinking and problem solving skills.
- CO3:** Learn to use modern tools and techniques.
- CO4:** Communicate effectively and to present ideas clearly and coherently both in written and oral forms.
- CO5:** Develop skills to work in a team to achieve common goal.
- CO6:** Develop skills of project management and finance.
- CO7:** Develop skills of self-learning, evaluate their learning and take appropriate actions to improve it.
- CO8:** Prepare them for life-long learning to face the challenges and support the technological changes to meet the societal needs.

Project Work Phase - II: Each student of the project batch shall involve in carrying out the project work jointly in constant consultation with internal guide, co-guide, and external guide and prepare the project report as per the norms avoiding plagiarism.

Evaluation Procedure:

- As per University guidelines
- Internal Marks: The Internal marks (100 marks) evaluation shall be based on Phase wise completion of the project work, Project report, Presentation and Demonstration of the actual/model/prototype of the project.

- Semester End Examination: SEE marks for the project (100 marks) shall be based on Project report, Presentation and Demonstration of the actual/model/prototype of the project, as per the University norms by the examiners appointed

**VIII Semester B.Tech
INTERNSHIP**

Sub Code : 17SCV86

Hrs/ Week : 3

Credits : 2

IA Marks : 50

Exam Hours: 2

Exam Marks: 50

Note: Internship /Professional Practice:

1. This shall be carried out by students in industry set-up related to the construction/ materials testing Laboratories/research organizations/project management consulting firms/QS and QA organizations/ Planning and design offices/Professional organizations like ACCE/ICI/INSTRUCT/RMCMA/QCI, PMI, CIDC etc. and other avenues related to the civil engineering domain in consultation and approval of internship guide/HOD /internship committees of the institutions.
2. The professional certification programs like ACCE(I)- SMP, ICI-BMTPC certifications, NSTRUCT certifications, CIDC certifications, RMC-QCI's RMCPCS Certification Programs, RMCMA-NRMCA'S Concrete Technologist India (CTI) programs and such similar programs by professional bodies with adequate industry exposures at sites/RMC plants can be considered as Internship /Professional Practice with due approvals from the guide/HOD /internship committees of the institutions.
3. The industry/organization should issue certificates of internship offer and its completion. The offer letter should clearly have the nature of work to be done by the student and the supervisor's name and duration of internship.
4. The student shall make a midterm and final presentation of the activities undertaken during the first 6 weeks and at the end of 12th week of internship respectively, to a panel comprising internship guide, a senior faculty from the department and head of the department. Each student should submit the internship report at the end of semester with internship certificate.
5. Viva-Voce examination shall be conducted by a panel of examiners consisting of internship supervisor from industry or industry professional approved by university and internship guide from the institute.
6. The College shall facilitate and monitor the student internship program.
7. The internship should be completed during vacation after VI and VII semesters.